

کانون پزشکی و حقوق ایران

Ph.D. Thesis

Analysis of antioxidant capacity of red blood cells in oxidative stress conditions utilizing fluorescent lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM)

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**Analiza pojemności antyoksydacyjnej krwinek czerwonych
w warunkach stresu oksydacyjnego z wykorzystaniem
fluorescencyjnej mikroskopii obrazowania życia (FLIM)**

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Dedication

In recognition of the inspiring pursuit of democracy by the people of Iran, a driving force that has imbued my career with purpose, I humbly dedicate this thesis. Additionally, I extend this dedication to my unwavering family, whose steadfast support has been a pillar of strength throughout my journey.

Memorial:

To my father Col. (Sarhang) Abdul-Majid Davoudpour (1944-2012) who left us during my scientific journey. your legacy will be with us in the pursuit of knowledge and commitment of excellence.

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Abstract

Abstract:

Oxidative stress-induced changes in cellular components often play a crucial role in various biological processes. In this study, we investigated the effects of oxidative stress on red blood cells (RBCs) using advanced fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) techniques. By employing alloxazine derivatives, such as lumichrome and 5Deaza alloxazine, as fluorescent probes, we examined the alterations in RBCs' fluorescence lifetimes under different conditions. Additionally, we explored the interactions between these probes and oxidized cholesterol residues on synthetic lipid membranes.

Our results revealed that oxidative stress induced by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) led to distinct changes in the fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs, attributed to various photochemical processes involving Hb oxidation, lipid peroxidation, and membrane alterations. We employed FLIM to differentiate between different metabolic states of RBCs and observed that prior incubation with the antioxidant trolox (Tx) shifted the fluorescence lifetime distribution, indicating potential protective effects on RBCs' oxidative conditions.

Furthermore, the interaction between alloxazine derivatives and oxidized cholesterol on lipid membranes was investigated. Despite no direct interaction being observed, the hydrophobic nature of the interactions was suggested. Our study sheds light on the intricate molecular mechanisms underlying oxidative stress-induced changes in RBCs and provides insights into the potential applications of FLIM as a sensitive, label-free method for monitoring cell metabolic states and oxidative stress in a non-invasive manner.

Keywords: oxidative stress, red blood cells, fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), alloxazine derivatives, lipid peroxidation, antioxidant, synthetic lipid membrane, cholesterol, hydrophobic interaction.

Abstrakcyjny

Stres oksydacyjny często odgrywa kluczową rolę w różnych procesach biologicznych, wpływając na zmiany w składnikach komórkowych. W niniejszym badaniu zbadaliśmy efekty stresu oksydacyjnego na krwinki czerwone (RBC) za pomocą zaawansowanej techniki mikroskopii obrazowania czasu życia fluorescencji (FLIM). Wykorzystując pochodne aloksazyny, takie jak lumichrom i 5-deaza aloksazyna, jako sondy fluorescencyjne, zbadaliśmy zmiany czasów życia fluorescencji RBC w różnych warunkach. Dodatkowo badaliśmy interakcje między tymi sondami a utlenionymi resztkami cholesterolu na syntetycznych błonach lipidowych.

Nasze wyniki ujawniły, że stres oksydacyjny wywołany przez nadtlenuk tert-butyłu (TB) prowadził do wyraźnych zmian w dystrybucji czasów życia fluorescencji RBC, co można przypisać różnym procesom fotochemicznym związanym z utlenianiem Hb, peroksydacji lipidów i zmianami w błonie. Zastosowaliśmy FLIM do różnicowania różnych stanów metabolicznych RBC i zaobserwowaliśmy, że wcześniejsze inkubowanie z antyoksydantem trolox (Tx) przesunęło dystrybucję czasów życia fluorescencji, wskazując na potencjalne efekty ochronne na stany oksydacyjne RBC.

Ponadto zbadaliśmy interakcję między pochodnymi aloksazyny a utlenionym cholesterolem na syntetycznych błonach lipidowych. Pomimo braku bezpośredniej interakcji, sugerowano hydrofobową naturę tej interakcji. Nasze badanie rzuciło światło na złożone mechanizmy molekularne leżące u podstaw zmian wywołanych stresem oksydacyjnym w RBC oraz dostarcza wglądu w potencjalne zastosowania FLIM jako wrażliwej, bezznakowej metody monitorowania stanów metabolicznych komórek i stresu oksydacyjnego w sposób nieinwazyjny.

Słowa kluczowe: stres oksydacyjny, krwinki czerwone, mikroskopia obrazowania czasu życia fluorescencji (FLIM), pochodne aloksazyny, peroksydacja lipidów, antyoksydant, syntetyczna błona lipidowa, cholesterol, interakcja hydrofobowa.

Introduction

Introduction

Fluorescence and its applications

Fluorescence, a phenomenon wherein a fluorescent substance emits light subsequent to its excitation by light or electromagnetic radiation, is a three-stage process prevalent in polyaromatic hydrocarbons or hetero-cycles referred to as fluorophores or fluorescent dyes (as detailed in the Handbook of Molecular Probes by Invitrogen). The three successive stages encompass:

1. Excitation
2. Lifetime within the excited state
3. Emission

These stages are effectively illustrated in the Jablonski diagram [1], which will be expounded upon later in this chapter. The fluorescence process is cyclic, except in instances where the fluorophore succumbs to destruction in the excited state through a phenomenon known as photobleaching.

Molecular fluorescence exhibits distinct characteristics, namely:

- I) Fluorescence spectra $I(\lambda)$, which signifies fluorescence intensity as a function of wavelength.
- II) Quantum yield Φ , denoting the ratio between the total count of emitted photons (nf) released during the fluorescence process and the total count of molecules elevated to the excited state (n).
- III) Fluorescence lifetime τ , a kinetic parameter inversely tied to the summation of rate constants encompassing both radiative process k_f and nonradiative processes k_{nr} , collectively identified as quenching[2].

Equation 1

$$\tau = \frac{1}{k_f + k_{nr}}$$

Jablonski diagram

Alexander Jablonski (1898-1980) devoted his entire lifetime to the comprehensive investigation of molecular absorption and emission processes of light [3]. Among his notable contributions, the Jablonski diagram stands as a profound achievement, depicting energy states along the vertical axis. Each column typically corresponds to a distinct spin multiplicity characteristic of a given species. For a specific molecule, the horizontal lines within each column delineate excited singlet states, with bold horizontal lines denoting the boundaries of electronic energy states. Within each electronic energy state, a multitude of vibrational energy states may be interconnected with the electronic state. Due to the considerable abundance of vibrational states, only a select few are displayed in each diagram. Moreover, these vibrational energy states can be further subdivided into rotational energy levels. It is noteworthy, however, that traditional Jablonski diagrams omit an intricate depiction of such extensive rotational details as the electronic energy state escalates. As the electronic energy levels draw nearer, the overlap of vibrational energy levels increases [4].

Figure 1 Jablonski Diagram depicting (A) Single Photon Excitation (1PE) and (B) Two Photon Excitation (2PE) processes, adapted from reference [4]. Energy levels are portrayed as horizontal lines, and electron transitions between these states are illustrated as vertical lines. The ground state, along with the first and second electronic excited states, is denoted as S₀, S₁, and S₂, respectively. The first triplet state is labeled as T₁. A dashed line signifies potential vibrational states.

Principles of single photon excitation and two photon excitation (1PE and 2PE)

Fluorescence occurs when photons of energy $h\nu_{ex}$ are emitted by an external source such as a lamp or a laser and are absorbed by fluorescence dyes and as explained earlier excites the electron to the electronic singlet state S_1 .

Where $h\nu$ is the Planck's constant [5] and ν_{ex} is the frequency of light or excitation to occur the energy of the absorbed photon has to be approximately equal to the energy difference between S_0 and excited states S_n . 1PE uses UV or visible light to excite fluorophore of interest continuously. Excitation occurs when the absorbed photon energy matches the energy gap between the ground and excited states (Figure 2). The same transition can be excited by a two-photon process in which two less energetic quantum lights with a sum frequency which is similar to the excitation frequency of the atom are simultaneously absorbed [6] A comparison between one- and two-photon absorption is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 The emitted fluorescence remains spectrally distinct from the excitation process, consistently aligning itself in proximity to the wavelength employed in Single Photon Excitation (1PE). Furthermore, it maintains a significant separation from the infrared (IR) wavelength associated with Two Photon Excitation (2PE). Notably, the use of near-infrared wavelengths for excitation results in the activation of the fluorophore within the visible wavelength range.

Quantum mechanically in 2PE a single photon excites the molecule to a virtual intermediate state and the molecule is eventually brought to the final excited state by the absorption of the second photon [7]

ROS production by photosensitizers

Photosensitizers are molecules which upon absorption of light energy are able to produce electrochemical changes in their neighboring molecules by abstracting or donating hydrogen molecules, they are responsible for the oxidative stress of biological samples both *in vivo* and *in vitro* and they are used as means of various therapeutical applications i.e. photodynamic therapy. Atomic oxygen has two unpaired π electrons in separate orbits in its principal energy level which makes it susceptible to form ROS (see figure 4), Different type of ROS are produced in cell mostly during electron transport in mitochondria.

Figure 3 representation of molecular oxygen lowest triplet and singlet states 95 kJ mol^{-1} ($22.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and 158 kJ mol^{-1} ($31.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) above the triplet state respectively [39](A) electron structures of common reactive oxygen species. Structures are provided with chemical formula. The red $\cdot$ designates an unpaired electron (B)

We already know that photooxidants produce ROS upon absorption of photons. Excited photosensitizer creates reactive dioxygen species in two types of reactions, sensitizer excitation is achieved by a single photon transition between the ground states S_0 and a singlet excited S_n . Relaxation of the S_n state yields lower singlet state of the sensitizer S_1 . Intersystem crossing (ISC) generates T_1 and lifetime of the T_1 state

is longer (ms) than that of the S₁ state (ns) allowing this excited state to react in one of two ways, defined as Types I and II mechanisms[8] in Type I mechanism a hydrogen-atom is abstracted or an electron transfers between the excited sensitizer and a substrate which yields free radicals. Reaction of these radicals with oxygen may form an active oxygen species such as the superoxide anion.

In a Type II mechanism singlet oxygen is generated when an excited sensitizer collides with triplet oxygen and energy transfer takes place. (See figure 5) Triplet states have a relatively long lifetime and high energy and therefore are highly reactive, rendering the fluorophore vulnerable to downstream reactions[9].

Where P is photosensitizer, S₀ singlet ground state; S₁ first excited singlet state; T₁ first excited triplet state; k_{ISC}, rate constant of intersystem crossing; k_{en}, rate

Figure 4 A simplified Jablonski diagram representing generation of excited sensitizers states and reactive dioxygen species[39]

constant of energy transfer; ³O₂ ground state triplet oxygen; and ¹O₂ singlet oxygen. Production of ROS for each fluorophore depends on its quantum yield. Quantum yield of many biophysical and biochemical interaction may compete with reactions (3) and (4)

Physical reactions with molecular oxygen or electron transfer, also compete with energy transfer

From equations (3) to (8) quantum yield is calculated as [10]

Equation 9
$$\phi_{\Delta} = \phi_T \phi_{en} = \phi_T \frac{k_{en}[O_2]}{k_r + k_{nr} + k_q[O_2]}$$

Where here ϕ_T is the quantum yield of triplet formation; ϕ_{en} , efficiency of energy transfer; k_{en} , rate constant of energy transfer; and k_q , sum of rate constants from the quenching of $P(T_1)$.

Principle of fluorescence lifetime

After absorption of photons with sufficient energy, a chain of photophysical events occurs in fluorophores including Internal conversion (IC), vibrational relaxation (loss of energy in the absence of light emission), fluorescence, ISC from singlet state to a triplet state and as shown in the Jablonski diagram (see Figure 1) Probability that each mentioned event happens is characterized by decay rate constants (K). Average length of time τ for the set of molecules decay rate for a set of molecules is proportional to :

Equation 10
$$\tau = 1/k$$

average lifetime (τ) is duration that is needed for N electronically excited molecules to be reduced by a factor of e . Correspondingly, the fluorescence lifetime is the time required by a population of excited fluorophores to decrease exponentially to N/e via the loss of energy through fluorescence and other non-radiative processes[2]. Fluorescence lifetime is traditionally considered to be a kinetic parameter and is determined as being inversely proportional to the sum rate constants of a radiative process k_f and the non-radiative[2] processes k_{nr} collectively known as quenching (Eq. 9).

Lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM)

Measuring fluorescence lifetime, time duration that fluorophore remains in excited state, provides us with an extra dimension to deal with many chemical and physical cues. With development of biosensors, it is intriguing to observe in realtime, complexities of cellular and biomolecular processes. Fluorophores and especially fluorescent proteins are exceedingly used in the current life sciences and since they are very sensitive to environmental changes some of their parameters for example their lifetime may be used to study lateral factors after for example to measure environmental pH or redox state.

Figure 5 lifetime decay curves of donor(green), acceptor (gray), FRET pair (red) and auto fluorescence (orange), delay time is the period between initial trigger due to the laser pulse. Measurement starts after the instrument response function (IRF) that should be deducted from the curve either manually (tailfit) or by mathematical deconvolution.

Several fluorescence lifetime imaging (FLIM) microscopes such as wide field imaging and confocal and multiphoton scanning systems are available nowadays. They are similar in principle that they all depend on an acquisition computer which registers a start signal (irradiation point) and a stop signal (end of fluorescence decay). Pulsed lasers drive discrete bursts of light for FLIM because in different modulation frequencies (between 1-200 MHz) which is suitable to image most fluorophores which have a range of few nanoseconds. A photomultiplier tube (PMT) then records fluorescence from the sample until the next laser pulse arrives, which signals that the

process has stopped. In this interval the sample is necessarily decayed. Two acquisition methods are commonly used to determine the fluorescence lifetime of fluorophores, time-domain and frequency-domain. Which are mathematically equivalent and their data can be interconverted through Fourier transform.

Figure 6 photon detection in a photodiode represented in a simple space-time diagram[79]. Photons entering the diode first pass through the silicon dioxide layer and then through the n and p layers before entering the depletion region where they excite free electrons and holes, which then migrate to the cathode and anode, respectively. When a semiconductor diode has a reverse voltage bias applied and the crystal junction between the p and n layers is illuminated, then a current will flow in proportion to the number of photons incident upon the junction. [80].

Frequency domain FLIM¹

In the frequency-domain Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM) technique, a modulated light source is employed to excite fluorophores, while a modulated detector captures the resulting emission. The process involves the modulation or pulsing of the excitation light's intensity at a specific radio frequency, typically within the range of 1 to 200 MHz.

As a consequence of this modulation, the induced fluorescence emission adopts a pattern that mirrors the modulation of the excitation light. Importantly, a temporal

¹ <https://www.lambertinstruments.com/technologies-1/2014/12/4/frequency-domain-flim-for-beginners>

delay manifests in the form of a phase-shift. Furthermore, the modulation depth undergoes reduction relative to the excitation light, whereas the overall average intensity remains consistent.

Both the phase-shift and modulation depth directly correlate with the fluorescence lifetime of the sample and are contingent upon the known modulation frequency. This interdependence between phase-shift, modulation depth, fluorescence lifetime, and modulation frequency forms the basis of the frequency-domain FLIM technique.

The sensitivity of the detector, often an intensified camera, is modulated or gated synchronously with the radio frequency of the light source. This synchronization enables the extraction of both phase shift and modulation depth from the fluorescence emission signal. Consequently, an intensity image is generated, characterized by a consistent brightness level.

For every pixel, a low-pass signal is generated by incrementally adjusting the phase of the image intensifier in relation to the light source. The resultant image's brightness is contingent upon whether the detector's sensitivity is in or out of phase with the fluorescence emission. This procedure yields a frequency-domain Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM) signal, delineating the phase difference between the light source and the camera for each pixel within the image.

Significantly, this frequency-domain signal is a direct reflection of the phase shift and demodulation that transpire in the time domain. Both the phase and modulation depth can be precisely deduced from the measurements, representing essential data in a homodyne FLIM measurement.

Determination of χ^2 (fitting) in frequency domain FLIM²

The observables to be measured in FD FLIM are, for each modulation frequency ω , the phase delay (φ) and the amplitude modulation ratio (m). The reduced χ^2 function is defined by Equation 11:

² https://iss.com/resources/pdf/technotes/FLIM_Using_Phazor_Plots.pdf

Equation 11

$$\chi^2 = \frac{1}{2n - p - 1} \left\{ \sum_{k=1}^n \left[\frac{\varphi_k - \varphi_{ck}}{\delta_{qk}} \right]^2 + \sum_{k=1}^n \left[\frac{m_k - m_{ck}}{\delta_{mk}} \right]^2 \right\}$$

- **n**: Number of modulation frequencies.
- **p**: Number of fitting parameters.
- **φ_k** and **m_k** : Measured phase shift and modulation ratio at frequency k .
- **φ_{ck}** and **m_{ck}** : Calculated phase shift and modulation ratio at frequency k , using estimated fitting parameters based on the selected decay model.
- **$\sigma_{\varphi k}$** and **σ_{mk}** : Uncertainties in phase and modulation ratio values, respectively.

Where n is the number of modulation frequencies; p is the number of the fitting parameters; φ_k and m_k are the measured phase shift and modulation ratio, while φ_{ck} and m_{ck} are the calculated phase shift and modulation ratio using the estimated fitting parameters based on the selected decay model, at frequency k ; $\sigma_{\varphi k}$ and σ_{mk} are the uncertainties in the phase and modulation ratio values, respectively. Indeed, the acquired modulation depth and phase shifts serve as valuable inputs for the calculation of two distinct and independent determinations of fluorescence lifetime. However, to achieve an absolute determination of fluorescence lifetime, a crucial step involves calibrating the system at the pixel level. This calibration process necessitates the use of a reference fluorophore with a known lifetime. Remarkably, the calibration requirement is straightforward: conducting a FLIM acquisition of the reference fluorophore possessing the established and verified lifetime. This empirical calibration process aligns the acquired modulation depth and phase shift data with a reliable reference, thereby enabling accurate and absolute fluorescence lifetime determination across the pixel spectrum.

Time domain FLIM

In the time domain the fluorescence decay can be measured by using time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) or fast-gated image intensifiers. A measurement requires short excitation pulses of high intensity and fast detection circuits. Each point in the sample is excited sequentially. TCSPC records a histogram of photon arrival times at each spatial location using Photo Multiplier Tubes (PMTs) or comparable single photon counting detectors. Fast-gated image intensifiers measure fluorescence intensity in a series of different time windows. With both time domain techniques lifetimes are derived from exponential fits to the decay data. When sufficient channels (time windows) are used, multi-exponential lifetimes can be extracted.

Time correlated single photon counting

Time-Correlated Single Photon Counting (TCSPC) stands as a precision technique for the discrete counting of individual photons, enabling the instantaneous detection of each photon's arrival time. This method capitalizes on the probabilistic distribution governing the emission of a single photon [45].

In essence, TCSPC entails the utilization of a pulsed light source to elicit fluorescence within a given fluorophore. Concurrently, a triggering mechanism initiates the timing process, which halts upon the arrival of the initial photon. The acquired data manifests as histograms, graphing photon counts against corresponding time intervals. These time measurements are stored in memory, and the excitation sequence is reiterated multiple times.

Upon scrutinizing the cumulative histogram of fluorescence emissions, it becomes possible to approximate the fluorescence lifetime of the fluorophore(s) in question. In a complementary manner, autocorrelation of the temporal photon count data offers crucial insights into various dynamic properties and interactions within the system under examination.

Measured data can offer also information on diffusion processes and fluorophore concentration. This method allows microwatt excitation powers for imaging of sensitive probes for a longer time. In time-domain, a pulsed laser excites the sample with pulse width $< 1-2$ ns with sufficient gap between incoming pulses. Among different

fluorescence detection methods time-correlated single photon counting (TCSPC) has simplified data collection and enhanced quantitative photon counting.

As detectors, Photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) or avalanche photodiodes (APDs) can be used to record emitted photons after each pulse in a time-dependent manner. During a excitation cycle average number of photons that arrive, z_i collide with PMT between time interval $T_{i-1/2}$ and $T_{i+1/2}$ these photons discharge an average number of photoelectron, w_i from photocathodes[11]

Equation 12

$$w_i = qz_i$$

In an APD incoming photons enter the diode first and pass through the silicon dioxide (SiO₂) ,Ar layer or etc. and then before entering depletion region, they excite free electron and produce holes which migrate towards cathode and anode. Recurrently these electrons impinge with the atomic lattice, which in return releases new electrons after secondary ionization. These secondary electrons are again multiplied in an avalanche like effect. An APD produces a fast electrical pulse of several volts amplitude in response to photon detection (see figure 7).

By combining PMT front with an APD amplification stage we may design a neat instrument response without afterpulsing. A traditional TCSPC consists of a constant fraction discriminator (CFD) to sort out timing information precisely from detector signals by comparing the signal with and amplified or delayed version of itself. This helps to shrink instrument response function (IRF). Sync pulses are similar to the trigger signal, traditionally signals from the CFD and SYNC trigger are fed to a time to amplitude converter (TAC). The voltage obtained from the TAC is then fed to an analog to digital converter (ADC) which provides the digital timing value used to address the histogrammer. The histogrammer provides rapid readout and assigns the histogram memory to the digital values that it receives from the ADC. This is commonly done by fast digital logic e.g., in the form of field programmable gate Arrays (FPGA) or a microprocessor [12].

Figure 7 diagram of a traditional TCSPC system. CFD = Constant Fraction Discriminator, TAC = Time to Amplitude Converter, ADC = Analog to Digital Converter[47]

The typical emission decays obtained from TCSPC method are shown in Fig. 8. The fluorescence lifetime is calculated from the slope of the decay curve according to Equation 13 [2].

Equation 13

$$F(T) = F_0 e^{-t/\tau}$$

Where T is the time after absorption, τ is fluorescence lifetime and F_0 is intensity at $T=0$. An instrument response function which determines distribution of photons from pulse source is deconvoluted from the decay curve commonly by fitting the slope of lifetime decay curve after IRF.

Figure 8 lifetime of immobilized GFP on a coverslide in PBS, after excitation with second harmonic generator at 976 nm, data collected using a TCSPC.

Determination of χ^2 (fitting) in time domain FLIM

The observable to be measured in TCSPC FLIM is the number of photons in each acquisition bin (N). The reduced χ^2 function is defined by Equation 14:

$$\text{Equation 14} \quad \chi^2 = \frac{1}{n-p-1} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{[N(t_k) - N_c(t_k)]^2}{\sigma_k^2} = \frac{1}{n-p-1} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{[N(t_k) - N_c(t_k)]^2}{N(t_k)}$$

Where n is the number of acquisition bins; p is the number of the fitting parameters; $N(t_k)$ is the number of photons collected and $N_c(t_k)$ is the number of photons calculated from the estimated fitting parameters based on the chosen decay model, in each data acquisition bin k ; σ_k is the standard deviation, and for a large number of photon counts following the Poisson distribution it is equal to the square root of $N(t_k)$.

Phasor plot for FD FLIM

Phasor plots are graphical representation of fluorescence lifetime data in a global semi-circle. Acquired TCSPC and FD FLIM data are interconvertible. In FD FLIM data the location of each pixel represents both phase delay (φ) and the amplitude modulation ratio (m) for one modulation frequency (ω). After transformation by Equation 15 in the semi-circle, where g and s represent the values of two coordinates (G, S) of the phasor plot (Figure 9).

$$\text{Equation 15} \quad g(\omega) = m \cos(\varphi) \quad \text{and} \quad s(\omega) = m \sin(\varphi)$$

Phasor plot for TCSPC FLIM

In TCSPC FLIM, traces of decay data are recorded for each pixel location. Each decay trace can be plotted in as a single point phasor by transforming to sine and cosine of the measured data. In this conversion modulation frequency (ω) is equal to laser repetition angular frequency and is calculated by multiplying the laser repetition rate with 2π (Figure 9).

Equation 16

$$g(\omega) = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} I(t)\cos(\omega t)}{\int_0^{\infty} I(t)} \text{ and } s(\omega) = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} I(t)\sin(\omega t)}{\int_0^{\infty} I(t)}$$

To obtain correct values for fluorescence lifetime the phasor plot has to be calibrated by a sample with known fluorescence lifetime. For FD FLIM calibration process is performed before data acquisition, for TCSPC FLIM the sample with known lifetime is used to calibrate the phasor.

Phasor for complex species with multiple lifetimes

For multiple lifetime species ($N>1$) equations (Equation 15) can be rewritten as:

Equation 17

$$g = \sum_{i=1}^N (f_i g_i) \text{ and } s = \sum_{i=1}^N (f_i s_i)$$

Equation 18

$$g_i = \frac{1}{1+\omega^2 t_i^2} \text{ and } s_i = \frac{\omega t_i}{1+\omega^2 t_i^2}$$

Phasor plot of a complex species (g, s) is presented as a linear combination of multiple phasors, each (g_i, s_i) representing an individual species. This allows calculation of fractional contribution (f_i) of each species i to the total intensity.

Figure 9 Representation of global phasor plot

Generation of radical oxygen species (ROS)

Atomic oxygen has two unpaired π electrons in separate orbits in its principal energy level which makes it susceptible to form ROS (see figure 9). Different types of ROS are produced in cells mostly during electron transport in mitochondria. We already know

Figure 10 representation of molecular oxygen lowest triplet and singlet states 95 kJ mol^{-1} ($22.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and 158 kJ mol^{-1} ($31.5 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) above the triplet state respectively [39](A) electron structures of common reactive oxygen species. Structures are provided with chemical formula. The red • designates an unpaired electron (B)

that photooxidants produce ROS upon absorption of photons, excited photosensitizer creates reactive dioxygen species in two types of reactions, sensitizer excitation is achieved by a single photon transition between the ground states S_0 and a singlet excited S_n . Relaxation of the S_n state yields lower singlet state of the sensitizer S_1 .

Where $f_{\Delta}^T = \left(\frac{k_{en}}{k_q}\right)$ indicates the fraction of triplet states quenched by oxygen which yields $^1O_2$ (or efficiency singlet oxygen yield) and $P_{O_2}^T = \frac{k_q[O_2]}{k_r+k_{nr}+k_q[O_2]}$ represents the fraction of triplet states quenched by oxygen.

There are different methods to measure quantum yield of singlet oxygen generation including, direct measurement of luminescence at (1270 nm) upon relaxation of singlet oxygen, calorimetric technics and quantitative analysis of photooxidation reactions[8,10].

$(k_{en} + k_{dO_2} + k_{et})$. There is a different way of calculating quantum yield of singlet oxygen formation by:

$$\text{Equation 19} \quad \Phi_{\Delta} = \Phi_T \frac{k_q[O_2]}{k_r+k_{nr}+k_q[O_2]} \left(\frac{k_{en}}{k_q}\right) = \Phi_T f_{\Delta}^T P_{O_2}^T$$

Where $f_{\Delta}^T = \left(\frac{k_{en}}{k_q}\right)$ indicates the fraction of triplet states quenched by oxygen which yields $^1O_2$ (or efficiency singlet oxygen yield) and $P_{O_2}^T = \frac{k_q[O_2]}{k_r+k_{nr}+k_q[O_2]}$ represents the fraction of triplet states quenched by oxygen.

From S_2 , electron undergoes radiation less energy loss by an internal conversion(IC) and returns to S_1 , there it bounces back to the S_0 in the meantime it may or may not emit photons[4].

Equation 20

ISC generates T_1 and lifetime of the T_1 state is longer (ms) than that of the S_1 state (ns) allowing this excited state to react in one of two ways, defined as Types I and II mechanisms[8] in Type I mechanism a hydrogen-atom is abstracted or an electron transfers between the excited sensitizer and a substrate which yields free radicals. Reaction of these radicals with oxygen may form an active oxygen species such as the superoxide anion.

In a Type II mechanism singlet oxygen is generated when an excited sensitizer collides with triplet oxygen and energy transfer takes place. (See figure 5) Triplet states have a relatively long lifetime and high energy and therefore are highly reactive, rendering the fluorophore vulnerable to downstream reactions[9].

Equation 21

Equation 22

Where P is sensitizer, S_0 singlet ground state; S_1 first excited singlet state; T_1 first excited triplet state; k_{ISC} , rate constant of intersystem crossing; k_{en} , rate constant of energy

Figure 11 A simplified Jablonski diagram representing generation of excited sensitizers states and reactive dioxygen species[39]

transfer; $^3\text{O}_2$ ground state triplet oxygen; and $^1\text{O}_2$ singlet oxygen. Production of ROS for each fluorophore depends on its quantum yield. Quantum yield of many biophysical and biochemical interaction may compete with reactions (3) and (4)

Physical reactions with molecular oxygen or electron transfer, also compete with energy transfer

From equations (3) to (8) quantum yield is calculated as [10]

Equation 27
$$\Phi_{\Delta} = \Phi_T \Phi_{en} = \Phi_T \frac{k_{en}[\text{O}_2]}{k_r + k_{nr} + k_q[\text{O}_2]}$$

Where here Φ_T is the quantum yield of triplet formation; Φ_{en} , efficiency of energy transfer; k_{en} , rate constant of energy transfer; and k_q , sum of rate constants from the quenching of $P(T_1)$.

by O_2 ($k_{en} + k_{do2} + k_{et}$). There is a different way of calculating quantum yield of singlet oxygen formation by:

Equation 28
$$\Phi_{\Delta} = \Phi_T \frac{k_q[\text{O}_2]}{k_r + k_{nr} + k_q[\text{O}_2]} \left(\frac{k_{en}}{k_q} \right) = \Phi_T f_{\Delta}^T P_{\text{O}_2}^T$$

Human red blood cells

Red blood cells (RBC) are main cells of human blood , they have a well-known shape - a biconcave disk (*SEM image*) and cell shape and flexibility [13] is well maintained in the plasma membrane , they have relatively simple structure - no nucleus, no organelles (*TEM image*)[14] and Hemoglobin (Hb) is the main functional protein of RBC. Red blood cells are most studied cell type in the history of the life sciences starting with the microscopic observations of Jan Swammerdam in approximately 1660. Erythropoiesis and evolution of red blood cells (RBCs) is initiated with the pluripotent stem cells of the bone marrow [15]. These stem cells undergo proliferation and differentiation into progenitor committed cells and the into progressively maturing precursors and finally mature RBCs, white cells, and platelets [16]. The RBC is, thus, especially designed for the delivery of oxygen to the tissues providing all cells with the required oxygen where it is used as a source of electrons and ATP synthesis in the mitochondria[17]. This is done by the reversible binding of oxygen to the very large pool of tetrameric haemoglobin (two *a* chains and two *b* chains, each with associated heme group) contained in the cell[18,19]. As sole gas transporter [20]cooperative binding of oxygen and modulation of *in vivo* oxygen affinity is dependent to a number of allosteric factors, including pH, organic phosphates, and carbon dioxide[21]. The Luebering-Rapoport shunt, a side arm of Embden-Meyerhof pathway, produces 2,3-DPG (Figure 1), essential for the regulation of O₂ affinity

Recent proteomics studies indicate that haemoglobin (Hb) accounts for 95 to 97% of the cytosolic protein of RBCs. Both the biconcave shape with excess surface area and elasticity are necessary for the cell to deform and deliver oxygen to the tissues [18].

Figure 12 Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) and Transmission Electron Microscope (TEM) of RBCs[22] .

RBCs have a very important role in hemostasis of blood.

Oxidative stress in red blood cells

Eryptosis is a process by which the erythrocytes (red blood cells, RBCs) undergo programmed cell death. Eryptosis, which significantly shortens the lifespan of RBCs, occurs in injured cells due to several factors, including oxidative stress[23]. Eryptosis has been documented in a range of medical conditions, including diabetes, liver failure, chronic kidney disease, malignancy, and inflammation . Moreover, this phenomenon plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of various disorders, such as malaria, sickle cell anemia, thalassemia, hemolytic uremic syndrome, G6PD deficiency, and Wilson's disease[24–26]. Eryptosis initiation hinges on the activation of Ca^{2+} -permeable cation channels, serving as a pivotal signaling pathway . This activation triggers an influx of Ca^{2+} into the erythrocytes (RBCs), which, in turn, prompts membrane scrambling and the exposure of phosphatidylserine (PS) . Moreover, the rise in intracellular Ca^{2+} levels activates Ca^{2+} -sensitive K^{+} channels, resulting in the efflux of cellular KCl and consequent cellular shrinkage [27–29].

Oxygen binding of Hb is dependent on keeping the heme iron in the less stable ferrous state (Fe^{2+}) in an oxidizing environment. In the absence of cellular reduction systems, the heme iron in proteins tends to autoxidize to the ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) form, which makes Hb unable to bind oxygen. This process is roughly equivalent to the iron “rusting” in an oxidizing environment[30]. The other properties of RBC are necessary to facilitate this oxygen binding and delivery. Experimental evidence indicates that RBCs are also important communication systems between different organs and can carry out additional functions, including their contribution in controlling systemic nitric oxide metabolism, redox regulation, blood rheology and viscosity[31].

Most of the other RBCs cytosolic proteins are involved in neutralizing oxidants like peroxiredoxin2 (PRDX2), catalase, superoxide dismutase (SOD) and glutathione peroxidase (GPx) and in ATP synthesis and the metabolism of glucose and (both anaerobic glycolysis and the hexose monophosphate shunt[32] [33] which will be discussed later.

RBCs are continuously exposed to both endogenous and exogenous sources of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can damage the RBC and impair its function in the circulation [34]. ROS are oxygen-centered molecules that include non-radicals hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) and singlet oxygen as well as radicals superoxide anion ($\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$), hydroxyl radical ($\text{HO}^\bullet$), and nitric oxide (NO) [35].

Atomic oxygen has two unpaired π electrons in separate orbitals in its principal energy level which makes it susceptible to form ROS (see figure). Different types of ROS are produced in cells mostly during electron transport in mitochondria. The addition of one electron to O_2 produces the $\text{O}_2^\bullet$ [36] which is a progenitor for other ROS whereas addition of two electrons results in formation of H_2O_2 . H_2O_2 can react with $\text{O}_2^{\bullet-}$ and ferric or cupric ions to produce the highly reactive $\text{HO}^\bullet$ which is most harmful for biological systems [35,37].

To reduce the impact of these ROS and the consequent oxidative stress, RBCs have a complex antioxidant system involving both non-enzymatic low molecular weight antioxidants like glutathione and ascorbic acid and enzymatic antioxidants including glutathione peroxidase [GPx] which has been shown to neutralize internal peroxides [38], catalase which is believed to have a main role to protect against external free radicals [39], superoxide dismutase (SOD) which catalyses the dismutation of superoxide ($\text{O}_2^\bullet$) to hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2); [40] and peroxiredoxin-2 (PRDX-2) [41] [18] therefore RBCs show less effects of cumulative oxidative damage in healthy conditions. Studies indicate that RBCs also contain NADH oxidases, which can generate endogenous ROS [42]. Sick cells ROS production can be induced by plasma signalling molecules.

Endogenous ROS generation

Endogenous ROS is generated as a result of both enzymatic and non-enzymatic reactions, enzymatic reactions which serve as source of free radicals, include those involved in the respiratory chain, in phagocytosis, in prostaglandin synthesis, and in the cytochrome P-450 system[43], Free radicals can also be formed in nonenzymatic reactions of oxygen with organic compounds as well as those initiated by ionizing reactions.

Some internally generated sources of free radicals are[44]

- Mitochondria
- Xanthine oxidase
- Peroxisomes
- Inflammation
- Phagocytosis
- Arachidonate pathways
- Exercise
- Ischemia/reperfusion injury

immune reactions, enzymes such nitric oxide synthase and transition metal mediated oxidation[45] are also involved in endogenous ROS production.

Hb redox reactions is the major source of RBC oxidative stress and produces methemoglobin that can no longer carry oxygen and superoxide that rapidly dismutates to form hydrogen peroxide[34]. Hb oxidation to metHb occurs continuously both by intracellular and extracellular reactive oxygen species and also via exogenous and endogenous nitrites and nitric oxide[46]. When oxidized, the primary structure of Hb is altered by the establishment of disulfide cross-links between globin chains that make the molecule unstable, leading to the formation of Heinz bodies and, eventually, to a premature RBC removal [47]. MetHb is responsible for activation of endothelial heme oxygenase (HO), an inducible microsomal heme degradation "stress" protein, which is responsible for heme catabolism and yields biliverdin, carbon monoxide, and iron[48] [49]. The reactive free radical species generated by Hb reactions and the interactions of Hb with membrane and cytoskeleton proteins both induce oxidative stress and are involved in RBC aging and are dependent on oxygen pressure and other allosteric factors, in low oxygen tensions ($pO_2 = 62$ mm Hg) formation of Hb oxidation products is increasing, whereas high oxygen tensions ($pO_2 = 540$ mm Hg) reduces Hb oxidation *in vitro* [50], The bulk of these ROS are neutralized by the RBC cytosolic low molecular weight antioxidants and also enzymatic pathways. Cytochrome b5 mediates reductive pathways by NADH or NADPH-dependent metHb reductases and respectively keep the level of metHb in erythrocytes at less than 1% of the total hemoglobin under normal [51] [52]. One Isoform of NADH oxidase present in RBCs is located on the membrane[42]. The second pathway uses flavin as an electron carrier for the reduction of metHb, coupled with NADPH oxidation, catalysed by NADPH-dependent flavin reductase (FR). Relative to the cytb5–NADH system, The flavin–NADPH pathway has generally been rendered a minor contributor to the reduction of metHb and malfunction of the flavin–NADPH system in erythrocytes is not associated with a metHb-reduction-deficient phenotype[53]. The ability of the antioxidant system to neutralize the endogenous ROS is limited as the blood flows through the microcirculation and Hb becomes partially oxygenated. Thus, there is a dramatic increase in the rate of Hb autoxidation for partially oxygenated Hb[54]. cytoplasmic domain of band 3 (cdb3) is considered to be sole Hb binding site of RBCs membrane and Hb-cdb3 interaction is dependent largely on O_2 , therefore all oxygen-regulated pathways of RBC depend nevertheless on the reversible association of deoxyHb with cdb3[55]. This sketch leading to consequent transmembrane conformational changes of cdb3-associated proteins which affects its affinity to Oxygen [56].

Cytochrome b5 reductase

Several researches have been dedicated to study Cytochrome b5 reductase (cb5r, EC 1.6.2.2) because it is involved in many Redox reactions including reduction of metHb to Hb. Cytochrome b5 reductase catalyses the transfer of reducing equivalents from NADH, via an FAD prosthetic group to two small molecules of cytochrome b5[57]. Two types of pyridine nucleotide dehydrogenase related to the reduction of metHb were separated by Scott, each of these enzymes is divided further into two species, NADH dehydrogenase I and II and NADPH-dehydrogenase A and B[58]. NADH-dehydrogenase I (diphosphopyridine nucleotide diaphorase) is the major enzyme reducing metHb[59]. This enzyme was characterized as NADH-cytochrome b5 reductase. NADH is produced as a side-product in anaerobic glycolytic Embden-Mayerhof pathways which provides 2 ATP as an energy source for RBCs[60]. Each Cytochrome b5 reductase isoform is a flavoprotein that has a different cellular localizations[61]. The amphipathic microsomal isoform[62], which is found in all cell types but erythrocytes, consists of one hydrophobic membrane-anchoring domain and a larger hydrophilic flavin catalytic domain. In human erythrocytes both soluble cytochrome b5 reductase isoform and membrane bound isoform has been reported, soluble isoform, is a truncated protein that is encoded by an alternative transcript and consists of the larger domain only, membrane bound cytochrome b5 reductase like amphiphilic isoform has also been reported in erythrocytes in inner membrane side and is antigenically similar to the soluble isoform[63].

Flavin reductase

Methemoglobin is reduced by NADPH-flavin reductase of human erythrocytes through flavin, flavin mononucleotide (FMN) functions as an effective electron carrier with the enzyme to reduce metHb, especially in the absence of oxygen [51,64]

immune reactions, enzymes such as xanthine oxidase and nitric oxide synthase and transition metal mediated oxidation[45]

Exogenous ROS

RBCs are well known ROS scavengers, including H₂O₂. Glucose metabolism[65], cation transport[66], ATP release[67] into circulation and ankyrin binding³⁴ have all been reported to be oxygen-dependent processes in erythrocytes[68]. Some externally generated sources of free radicals are [44]:

- Cigarette smoke
- Environmental pollutants
- Radiation
- Certain drugs, pesticides
- Industrial solvents
- Ozone

RBC antioxidant system

An extensive antioxidant system is designed to neutralize the harmful reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated as a result of the constant exposure to variable oxygen tensions. However, a condition of oxidative stress develops when the critical balance between oxidants and antioxidants is disrupted due to depletion of antioxidants and/or excess accumulation of ROS [69].

Within tissues, the release of oxygen (O₂) from hemoglobin (Hb) entails a structural rearrangement of the globin chains. This conformational change permits the entry of 2,3-diphosphoglycerate (2,3-DPG), a molecule that effectively reduces the affinity of Hb for oxygen, facilitating O₂ unloading. [70]

Erythrocytes possess the ability to convert methemoglobin (metHb) back into functional hemoglobin (Hb) via enzymatic action facilitated by methemoglobin reductases. Additionally, these cells engage in the detoxification of hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) by means of the intricate glutathione metabolic pathway. [60].

MetHemoglobin reductases

To restore functional efficacy of hemoglobin, the requisite transformation of methemoglobin (ferrihemoglobin) to hemoglobin (ferrohemoglobin) is imperative. This vital metabolic conversion is predominantly orchestrated by the red cell enzyme NADH-cytochrome b₅ reductase (NADH-methemoglobin reductase) within the physiological milieu. The efficiency of this enzymatic process is so pronounced that minute quantities of methemoglobin persist within the bloodstream under normal physiological circumstances [71]. NADH diaphorase: a hereditary variant linked to unimpaired methemoglobin reduction [72]. The absorption spectra of the isolated enzyme exhibit distinctive features typical of flavoproteins, displaying absorption peaks at 225 nm, 273 nm, 393 nm, and 462 nm, accompanied by absorption shoulders at 430 nm and 488 nm. Notably, the absorbance ratio at 273 nm to 462 nm is measured at 6.1 for the enzyme [73].

GSH metabolism

Approximately 80-90% of the glucose entering the cell is directed along the Embden-Meyerhof pathway, while the remaining 10% undergoes metabolic processing via the pentose phosphate pathway [12]. This parallel process yields ribose-5-phosphate and concurrently generates NADPH, as illustrated in Figure 1. The NADPH molecule serves a critical role in facilitating glutathione (GSH) metabolism, which in turn ensures effective detoxification of red blood cells (RBCs) from reactive oxygen species (ROS). Thus, NADPH represents a pivotal component of the erythrocyte's antioxidant defense mechanism. [47]

Functioning as a potent antioxidant defense, glutathione (GSH) undertakes various roles, including its direct scavenging of hydroxyl radicals and peroxynitrites. [74,75] it is involved in lipid peroxide detoxification [76] In the presence of glutathione peroxidase (GPx), GSH effectively reduces hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) by utilizing its thiol group. Additionally, GSH plays a crucial role in maintaining the reduced state of thiol groups within hemoglobin (Hb), enzymes, and membrane proteins. This activity is essential for safeguarding the functional integrity of these biomolecules. [77], This mechanism is of paramount importance for maintaining the integrity of erythrocyte functions. The preservation of thiol groups within these cells is crucial, as their oxidation could result in significant functional and structural alterations. Consequently, the ratio of reduced glutathione (GSH) to oxidized glutathione (GSSG) assumes a critical role, serving as a vital indicator of the cellular redox state. [75]

Reduced levels of glutathione (GSH) have been documented in both physiological phenomena like aging, and in pathological conditions characterized by oxidative stress (OS), such as Alzheimer's disease and Parkinson's disease. [75] sickle cell anemia and asthma [78]. Fraction of extracted GSH from blood shows a linear increase in fluorescence in 587 nm after supplementation in CTAB (cetyltrimethylammonium bromide) media buffer, the absorption spectra is around 280 nm[79].

Ascorbic acid

Ascorbic acid (AA), commonly known as vitamin C, holds significant physiological importance as an essential antioxidant and radical scavenger. Ascorbic acid (AA), primarily participates in one-electron transfer reactions, leading to the generation of ascorbate free radicals (AFR). However, it can also undergo further oxidation, relinquishing a second electron, resulting in the formation of dehydroascorbic acid (DHA)[80]. Under near-neutral pH conditions, the prevailing species is the monoanionic form of ascorbic acid, known as AsCH^- . Ascorbic acid and the AsCH^- monoanion exhibit discernibly distinct ultraviolet (UV) spectra. The diprotic form, AsCH_2 , displays a peak molar absorptivity at 243 nm, with a value of $\epsilon_{243}=9650 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ [81]. Conversely, the AsCH^- monoanion exhibits an absorption peak at 265 nm[82].

α tocopherol

Vitamin E, primarily in the form of α -tocopherol, stands as a crucial antioxidant, primarily tasked with safeguarding lipids against oxidative harm. In individuals afflicted with β -thalassemia major, the buildup of unpaired α -globin chains can give rise to clinical manifestations such as ineffective erythropoiesis, hemolysis, and persistent anemia. The combination of frequent blood transfusions and resultant iron overload contributes to cellular oxidative stress. Notably, α -tocopherol, an antioxidant agent, exhibits remarkable efficacy in neutralizing lipid radicals within the membranes of red blood cells (RBCs) in patients afflicted with β -thalassemia major. A significant correlation between absorption within the spectral range of 3200-2850 Å. and the purported biological activity of the tocopherols (vit. E)[83].

ROS production by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB)

Tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) PubChem ID 24865918 is a standard ROS producer which has been widely used in oxidative stress studies.

Figure 13 Time course for oxidative processes induced by the organic peroxide, TB, in human RBC [84].

Following exposure to tuberculosis (TB), cells undergo oxidative stress, characterized by a series of events:

1. Oxidation of reduced glutathione.
2. Oxidation of oxyhemoglobin (oxyHb).
3. Accumulation of methemoglobin (metHb).
4. Accumulation of the ferryl form of hemoglobin.
5. Peroxidation of membrane lipids, leading to the formation of thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS).
6. Alterations in oxygen tension within the red blood cell (RBC) suspension , as depicted in Figure 13 [84].

Subsequent to oxidative stress induced by TB exposure, cells exhibit fluorescence aging markers, including TBARS. These changes are concomitant with an elevation in the integral chemiluminescence curve (6) and are followed by a process of vesiculation.

After OS with TB cells show fluorescence aging markers including (TBARS). These changes are associated with an increase in integral chemiluminescence curve (6) proceeding with egzvisiculation .

Photochemistry of red blood cells

Endogenous fluorophores provide multiple possibilities to investigate several functions of the cell and to analyse biological processes, contributing to the unique optical properties of biomolecules. These natural fluorophores are separated with distinct excitation and emission characteristics, often accompanied by specific fluorescence lifetimes. A summary of some key endogenous fluorophores of the RBCs and their spectroscopic attributes is presented below:

1. Hemoglobin (Porphyrins):

Hemoglobin, a vital component of red blood cells, displays distinctive fluorescence properties attributed to its porphyrin structure [86]. Upon excitation at wavelengths ranging from 400 to 450 nm and 600 nm, hemoglobin emits light at around 440 nm and in the 600-750 nm range. The fluorescence lifetimes associated with these emissions are notably short, at approximately 0.2 ns and 1.54 ns, respectively [87].

2. Lipofuscin:

Lipofuscin, an age-related pigment formed from the oxidation of biomolecules, exhibits fluorescence when excited between 340 to 395 nm [88]. Its emission wavelengths range from 540 nm to 430-460 nm, with fluorescence lifetimes spanning 0.2 ns, 1.8 ns, and 6.3 ns. These fluorescence properties provide insights into cellular aging and oxidative stress.

3. Amino Acids:

Amino acids such as tryptophan, phenylalanine, and tyrosine contribute distinct fluorescent signals. Tryptophan, with an excitation wavelength of 280 nm and an emission range of 250-310 nm, undergoes complex fluorescence dynamics. Its fluorescence lifetime varies significantly depending on its environment, characterized by lifetimes of 0.016 ns, 0.820 ns, and 8.306 ns in oxyhemoglobin, and 0.009 ns, 0.901 ns, and 7.479 ns in deoxyhemoglobin [89]. Phenylalanine, when excited at 258 nm, emits light at 280 nm, with fluorescence lifetimes of 0.35 ns and 2.53 ns [90]. Tyrosine, excited at 275 nm, emits fluorescence at 300 nm, with a relatively longer lifetime of 3.4 ns [85, 91].

These distinct fluorescence characteristics enable the study of various biomolecules and their interactions within biological systems. The spectroscopic information obtained from these endogenous fluorophores serves as a valuable tool for understanding biochemical processes, cellular aging, and oxidative stress in different biological contexts.

Table 2: Spectral characteristics of RBC endogenous fluorophores. Some intrinsic fluorophores which are present in metabolically active cells like NADH has not been listed. *Hemoglobin excitation and emission maximum are different than the measured values in the table, the listed values represent optimal measurement parameters to reduce noise and interference with other fluorophores. † Shifts may be observed based on one or two photon excitation of Tyr [85]

Spectral characteristics of RBC endogenous fluorophores

Endogenous fluorophore	Excitation (nm)	Emission (nm)	Fluorescence lifetime (ns)	Reference
Hemoglobin (Porphyrins)	400-450, 600*	440, 600-750*	0.2, 1.54	[86,87]
Methemoglobin	600*	440, 600-750*		
Lipofuscin	340-395	540, 430-460	0.2, 1.8, 6.3	[88]
Amino acids				
Tryptophan	280	250-310		
-in oxy Hb			0.016, 0.820, 8.306	[89]
-in deoxy Hb			0.009, 0.901, 7.479	[89]
Phenylalanine	258	280	0.35, 2.53	[90]
Tyrosine	275	300	3.4	[85,91]

Objectives

Objectives

1. Analysis of anti-oxidant capacity of RBCs in oxidative stress conditions by measuring intrinsic fluorescence lifetime using FLIM histogram and phasor transformation

Red blood cells (RBCs) are the main cellular component (99%) of human blood.[92] The main function of RBCs is to transport oxygen from lung to all tissues in the body. Hemoglobin (Hb) is the main cytosolic protein of RBCs involved in oxygen binding dependent on the stability of the heme ferrous (Fe^{2+}) state. When the ferrous iron (Fe^{2+}) of the heme group of Hb is oxidized to ferric iron (Fe^{3+}), which is unable to bind oxygen, dysfunctional form of Hb, namely methemoglobin (metHb), is formed.[93] Under physiological condition, metHb is easily converted to Hb by nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NADH)-dependent cytochrome-b5 reductase (metHb reductase) and also, partially, by the endogenous antioxidants, such as glutathione and exogenous (dietary) antioxidants, such as ascorbic acid.[94] Therefore, the concentration of metHb in RBCs is maintained at very low (<1 %) level.[93] However, under oxidative stress conditions, caused by the overproduction of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and also by oxidizing drugs i.e. chloroquine and hydroxychloroquine, Hb may undergo constant autooxidation and dysfunctional metHb is formed in large amounts.[95] Such elevated metHb level in the blood is defined as methemoglobinemia, an uncommon condition which is well characterized by oxidised iron in the porphyrin group of heme from the ferrous (Fe^{2+}) to the ferric (Fe^{3+}). Recently it has been showed that methemoglobinemia can be found in certain severely ill COVID-19 patients.[96,97] When globin in Hb is denatured by prolonged ROS action, metHb converts to hemichrome, the main constituent of Heinz bodies, inclusions that are visible in intact RBCs stained with methyl violet.[98]

Hb contributes most in RBCs photochemical properties dependent on its form. Hb derivatives and mutant forms, have been studied to understand dynamics of O_2 binding and several other aspects of its photochemistry.[99] Hb photochemistry is a complex set of reactions leading to conversions of Hb from oxy- to deoxy- or to meth- forms. The absorption spectra of Hb exhibited two characteristic bands, Soret band and centered at about $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 415 \text{ nm}$ and Q-bands at $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 540 \text{ nm}$ and 578 nm .[100]

Broad emission spectrum of intact RBCs correspond to the several components: tryptophan (Trp), with an absorption band 260-290 nm ($\lambda_{ex} = 280 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{em} = 300\text{-}350 \text{ nm}$), [85,101] flavin adenine dinucleotides (FAD) ($\lambda_{ex} = 400 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{em} = 510 \text{ nm}$) and nicotinamide dinucleotide (NADH) ($\lambda_{ex} = 365 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{em} = 460 \text{ nm}$). [102]

The electronic absorption spectrum of a typical porphyrin like Hb is related to a strong transition to the second excited state ($S_0 \rightarrow S_2$) at about 400 nm (the Soret or B band) and weaker transitions to the first excited state ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$) at about 550 nm (the Q band). Internal conversion from S_2 to S_1 is rapid so fluorescence is only detected from S_1 . [103] Previously several spectrophotometric methods have been proposed to determine Hb subforms in toxicological studies i.e. by using first derivative of absorption spectrum at 500-600 nm or broadband spectral measurements. [104–106] Here, we employ FLIM which enables us to effectively observe autofluorescence of RBCs in physiological and under oxidative stress conditions, Analysis of FLIM data was performed both by applying the 'fit-free' phasor approach where each pixel of the image is transformed to its corresponding phasor on the phasor plot [107–109] and also comparing the FLIM lifetime histograms. Biological systems are complex to study their intrinsic autofluorescence, however, RBCs are good models because their main photochemical properties are related to Hb.

In current study we used *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (TB), as standard ROS generator, to induce the oxidative stress conditions and changes in Hb properties. Trolox (TX), a synthesized hydrophilic vitamin E analog (6-hydroxy-2,5,7,8-tetramethylchroman-2-carboxylic acid) was applied to as the standard antioxidant to reduce the oxidative stress conditions. [110] Fluorescence lifetime has been measured in ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em} = 375 \text{ nm}/460 \text{ nm}$) and also on the shoulder of Hb excitation and emission spectra ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em} = 640 \text{ nm}/690 \text{ nm}$) to reduce noise ratio.

Here we could observe and compare fractions of lifetimes presumably related to different subforms of Hb (oxyHb and metHb) by phasor plot analysis [108] and a traditional Gaussian fitting of fluorescence lifetime histograms. Afterwards we compared the accuracy of both methods. Phasor plots are characteristics of a given system [107,108] and phasor representation of fluorescence lifetime data could provide a graphical and fast signature of the collected data for complex biological systems in different studies when the collected photon were enough.

In this study, we introduce a straightforward setup for the assessment of red blood cell (RBC) photochemical attributes under diverse oxidative stress conditions using

Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM) coupled with phasor analysis. Notably, our investigation encompasses the ($\lambda_{ex}/\lambda_{em} = 640 \text{ nm}/690 \text{ nm}$) spectral range, which, to our best knowledge, has not been previously explored. This innovative approach to characterizing RBCs bears potential significance in various domains.

The outcomes of this characterization could prove valuable in the realm of *in vitro* experimental investigations, particularly concerning the assessment of the antioxidant and cytoprotective potential offered by novel antioxidants. Furthermore, our methodology holds promise in the evaluation of conditions like methemoglobinemia and other ailments impacting RBC functionality.

In parallel, we delve into the RBC's capacity to accommodate exogenous antioxidant Tx. To elucidate this facet, a preincubation protocol is employed, thus offering comprehensive insights into the interplay between intrinsic and extrinsic antioxidant mechanisms.

2. Double spectral analysis of RBC intrinsic fluorescence lifetime in oxidative stress conditions

Red blood cells stand as one of the most extensively studied cell types throughout the annals of life sciences. This legacy traces back to the pioneering microscopic observations made by Jan Swammerdam around 1660. The intricate journey of erythropoiesis and the evolution of red blood cells (RBCs) commences with the pluripotent stem cells found within the confines of the bone marrow. [15]. These stem cells undergo proliferation and differentiation into progenitor committed cells and the into progressively maturing precursors and finally mature RBCs, white cells, and platelets [16]. The RBC is, thus, especially designed for the delivery of oxygen to the tissues providing all cells with the required oxygen where it is used as a source of electrons and ATP synthesis in the mitochondria[17]. This is done by the reversible binding of oxygen to the very large pool of tetrameric haemoglobin (two *a* chains and two *b* chains, each with associated heme group) contained in the cell[18,19]. As sole gas transporter [20]cooperative binding of oxygen and modulation of *in vivo* oxygen affinity is dependent to a number of allosteric factors, including pH, organic phosphates, and carbon dioxide[21]. A significant biochemical pathway, known as

the Luebering-Rapoport shunt, operates as a subsidiary branch of the Embden-Meyerhof pathway. This pathway is responsible for generating 2,3-diphosphoglycerate (2,3-DPG), a crucial molecule pivotal in the fine-tuned regulation of oxygen affinity.

Comprehensive proteomic investigations unveil a compelling fact: hemoglobin (Hb) constitutes a substantial portion, ranging from 95% to 97%, of the cytosolic protein content within red blood cells (RBCs). The unique biconcave shape, coupled with a surplus of surface area and inherent elasticity, collectively endow RBCs with the requisite flexibility and deformability essential for their ability to navigate through circulation and effectively deliver oxygen to various tissues. [18].

The binding of oxygen to hemoglobin (Hb) hinges upon maintaining the heme iron in its relatively less stable ferrous state (Fe^{2+}), even within an oxidative environment. In situations where cellular reduction mechanisms are lacking, the heme iron within proteins is prone to autoxidation, transitioning to the ferric iron (Fe^{3+}) form. This oxidation renders Hb incapable of effectively binding oxygen. In essence, this phenomenon bears a resemblance to the process of iron "rusting" when exposed to an oxidizing milieu.[30]. Apart from their role in oxygen binding and delivery, red blood cells (RBCs) exhibit a range of complementary properties that are essential for these functions. Experimental findings underscore the significance of RBCs as intricate communication conduits connecting various organs within the body. Moreover, RBCs fulfill additional vital roles, encompassing the modulation of systemic nitric oxide metabolism, engagement in redox regulation, influence on blood rheology and viscosity, and various other contributions. These multifaceted functions highlight the complexity and importance of RBCs in maintaining overall physiological homeostasis.[31].

A substantial portion of the cytosolic proteins within red blood cells (RBCs) serve the crucial role of counteracting oxidative agents. Key examples of such proteins include peroxiredoxin 2 (PRDX2), catalase, superoxide dismutase (SOD), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx). Additionally, many RBC proteins are actively involved in vital processes, including ATP synthesis and the intricate metabolism of glucose. This metabolic role spans both anaerobic glycolysis and the hexose monophosphate shunt. The orchestration of these multifaceted functions collectively ensures the optimal

performance of RBCs in maintaining systemic equilibrium and functionality.[32] [33] which will be discussed later.

RBCs are continuously exposed to both endogenous and exogenous sources of reactive oxygen species (ROS) that can damage the RBC and impair its function in the circulation [34]. ROS are oxygen-centered molecules that include non-radicals hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and singlet oxygen as well as radicals superoxide anion (O₂^{•-}),

In the past decade, a number of new fluorescent probes, electron-spin resonance approaches, and immunoassays have been developed with higher selectivity for ROS detection [111]. Translation of the available methods to clinical applications however has been slower.

Exposure of RBC suspension to tert-butyl hydroperoxide **C₄H₁₀O₂** (TB), results in complex cellular chemical and biochemical reactions[84]. The chemistry of membrane-permeable TB interactions with RBCs has been studied well. in erythrocytes[84]. Most hydroperoxide is metabolized to non-radical products via two-electron reduction by glutathione peroxidase enzymes, and the glutathione disulfide (GSSG) produced is then

recycled. Glutathione peroxidase

As demonstrated in the equations below, however, hydroperoxides can generate free radicals via two major pathways, one-electron reduction to produce t-butoxyl and methyl radicals and one-electron oxidation to form t-butylperoxy radicals.

An extensive antioxidant system is available in the cells to neutralize the harmful reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated as a result of the constant exposure to variable oxygen tensions. However, a condition of oxidative stress develops when the critical balance between oxidants and antioxidants is disrupted due to depletion of antioxidants and/or excess accumulation of ROS [69]. Enzymatic pathways like Cytochrome b5 reductase, Flavin reductase, methHb reductases, GSH metabolism are shown to recover methHb to active oxyHb and protect the cells against OS (oxidative stress). also non-enzymatic α -tocopherol, ascorbic acid and glutathione has been marked important in cellular anti oxidative stress (OS) system[60]. Detection of radical species suggests that degradation of organic peroxides via one electron oxidation or

reduction are significant pathways. Of the two processes that generate radicals, one-electron reduction is believed to be the more important under normal conditions ([112]; [113]; [114]).

In our studies photochemical capacity of RBCs *in vitro* has been evaluated in different oxidative stress conditions induced by different concentrations of tert-butyl hydroperoxide (25, 100, 250 μ M TB) after preincubation with standard antioxidant Trolox (Tx) as a standard antioxidant and compared to four- alloxazine derivatives with extended aromaticity- naphtho[2,3-*g*]pteridine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione (**1a**) and 1,3-dimethylnaphtho[2,3-*g*]pteridine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione (**1b**) and also 5-deazaalloxazine (5DAI) using fluorescence lifetime image microscopy (FLIM). The data were also transformed and presented as phasor polar plot which enabled us to compare RBCs potential antioxidant capacity and to evaluate different compounds anti oxidant properties compared to Tx. Hemoglobin (Hb) is the main constituent of red blood cells (RBCs) and contributes most in the RBCs photochemical properties. A cluster of Phasor trajectories of Hb in RBCs in highly oxidized RBCs (presumably metHb) are visible after incubation with 250 μ M TB. Prior incubation of RBCs with antioxidants may present capacity of RBCs to employ exogenous antioxidants such as standard Tx and may preserve Hb subforms in RBCs as shown by analyzing FLIM histogram but not phasor analysis at least in lower concentrations (0.01 and 0.1 mg/ml), Analysis of FLIM histogram by multiple gaussian fits provides valuable information about sensitive changes of intrinsic fluorescence lifetime in oxidative stress (OS) conditions. The results of the experiment depends also to the concentration of the Tx. After preincubation with 1a and 1b and subsequently 5DAI we observed the changes in the fractional intensity of the shorter lifetime component suggesting potential anti oxidant properties for 5DAI and 1b. To induce oxidative stress (OS) we applied tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) which is an organic peroxide that is widely used in a variety of oxidation processes, RBC exposure to TB results in transient oxygen release followed by oxygen consumption. The oxygen release in red blood cells is associated with intracellular oxyHb oxidation with a pKa 6.7 ± 0.2 [115]. TB induced OS processes in human erythrocytes in parallel to free radical generation reduces glutathione oxidation and promotes oxyHb oxidation, metHb accumulation, ferryl form of Hb accumulation. Changes in O₂ tension in the RBC suspension has also been observed following TB incubation[84,115]

Unique spectral and temporal characteristic of human RBC both intrinsic fluorescence in different redox states and fluorescence in presence of some flavin and alloxazine derivatives as probe using a single photon time-resolved spectroscopic detection system and FLIM in $\lambda_{ex} = 640_{nm} / \lambda_{em} = 690 \text{ nm}$ which has not been reported previously. For flavins steady state absorbance and emission is very dependent on their redox states being in oxidized form, neutral and anionic semiquinones, and neutral and anionic fully-reduced hydroquinones[101] Our previous data confirms that properties of RBCs are changing after incubation with different concentration of TB as an oxidant and some isoalloxazine derivatives. Having in mind the report of efficacy of prior incubation of antioxidant trifluoperazine (TFP) [116] with the hepatocytes. In this study, we have utilized alternative derivatives to enhance the conditions impacted by (TB). We employed two distinct cell incubation protocols, integrating TB, Tx, and 5DAII. Subsequently, we have presented the graphical representation of fluorescence lifetime data in the form of phasor plots.

The primary objective of this research is to furnish a distinctive graphical fluorescence lifetime signature. This signature serves as a powerful analytical tool to assess oxidative stress (OS) within red blood cells (RBCs). We achieve this through the integration of Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy (FLIM) and phasor analysis. Our focus is on deciphering alterations in hemoglobin (Hb) properties induced by TB, alongside the application of Tx as a benchmark antioxidant. Notably, we intended to extend this methodology to encompass a spectrum of alloxazine derivatives.

3. Photobiology and molecular modelling of lumichrome and 5-deazaalloxazine in RBC and synthetic heterogenous lipid membranes

Red blood cells (RBCs) amongst eukaryotic cells have special characteristics because they have no nucleus or cytoplasmic structures or organelles [117]. Therefore, the structural properties are linked to the cell membrane. In addition to the lipid bilayer and integral proteins, RBC membrane possesses a 2D cytoskeleton tethered to the lipid bilayer. The RBC membrane cytoskeleton has a 2D six-fold structure and it is made of spectrin tetramers, connected at the actin junctional complexes, forming a 2D six-fold structure. The cytoskeleton is connected to the lipid bilayer via “immobile” band-3 proteins at the spectrin-ankyrin binding sites and via glycophorin protein at the actin junctional complexes [117]. To induce oxidative stress (OS) we applied tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) which is an organic peroxide that is widely used in a variety of oxidation processes, RBC exposure to TB results in transient oxygen release followed by oxygen consumption. The oxygen release in red blood cells is associated with intracellular oxyHb oxidation with a $pK_a 6.7 \pm 0.2$ [115]. TB induced OS processes in human erythrocytes in parallel to free radical generation reduces glutathione oxidation and promotes oxyHb oxidation, metHb accumulation, ferryl form of Hb accumulation. Changes in O_2 tension in the RBC suspension has also been observed following TB incubation [84,115]. Oxygen consumption in parallel with free radical generation leads to metHb production as revealed by absorption spectra in 500-600 nm area (Reference). Membrane and presumably peroxy radicals are produced after membrane lipid peroxidation (lipofuscin and ceroid pigments) usually named age pigments which are accompanied by the appearance of high molecular weight proteins or polymeric lipid-protein complexes. Having a strong fluorescence with a maximum in the region of 430–490 nm on excitation which have been characterized by several investigators with ultraviolet light. The pigments are probably composed of heterogeneous complexes including lipid-soluble and lipid-insoluble fluorescent lipid peroxidation products [118,119]. Fluorescence lifetime of extracted lipofuscin granules in chloroform are reported as 3 exponential 0.2 ns, 1.8 ns, 6.3 ns using similar setup [88].

Exposure of RBC suspension to TB, results in complex cellular chemical and biochemical reactions[84]. The chemistry of membrane-permeable TB interactions with RBCs has been studied well. in erythrocytes[84]. An extensive antioxidant system is available in the cells to neutralize the harmful reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated as a result of the constant exposure to variable oxygen tensions. However, a condition of oxidative stress develops when the critical balance between oxidants and antioxidants is disrupted due to depletion of antioxidants and/or excess accumulation of ROS [69]. Enzymatic pathways like Cytochrome b5 reductase, Flavin reductase, metHb reductases, GSH metabolism are shown to recover metHb to active oxyHb and protect the cells against OS (oxidative stress). also non-enzymatic α -tocopherol, ascorbic acid and glutathione has been marked important in cellular anti oxidative stress (OS) system[60].

Materials and Methods

Materials and methods

Reagents

Chemical and reagents including 5Dall (5-Deazaalloxazine), LChr(Lumichrome) and 4 ring alloxazine derivatives (- naphtho[2,3-*g*]pteridine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione (**1a**) and 1,3-dimethylnaphtho[2,3-*g*]pteridine-2,4(1*H*,3*H*)-dione (**1b**)) were provided by department of Spectroscopy and Magnetism, faculty of Chemistry, Adam-Mickiewicz university of Poznan-Poland by laboratory of Prof. Marek Sikorski. TB (tert-butyl hydroperoxide) and Trolox (Tx) were provided by faculty of Biology, Adam-Mickiewicz university of Poznan-Poland by laboratory of Prof. Dr. Lucyna Mrowczynska.

Human red blood cells

Fresh human red blood cell (RBC) concentrates, with a hematocrit level of 65%, were procured from the blood bank. This acquisition was conducted in adherence to bilateral agreement no. ZP/2867/D/21, a pact signed between the Regional Blood Center in Poznań and Adam Mickiewicz University in Poznań.

The RBC suspension underwent a thorough washing process, involving three rounds of centrifugation (3000 rpm, 10 min, +4°C), using phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) with a pH of 7.4. This PBS solution comprised 137 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM Na₂HPO₄, and 1.76 mM KH₂PO₄, supplemented with 10 mM glucose.

Following the washing steps, the RBCs were resuspended in a PBS buffer augmented with 10 mM glucose, attaining a concentration of 1.65×10^9 cells/mL (equivalent to a hematocrit level of 15%). These prepared RBC suspensions were stored at +4°C and were utilized within a span of 5 hours.

Treatment of RBCs with alloxazine derivatives

4 rings alloxazine derivatives, lumichrome, 5Dall

Red blood cells (RBCs) were utilized at a concentration of 1.65×10^9 cells/mL, corresponding to a hematocrit of 1.5%. The cells were subjected to an incubation

process in a PBS buffer with a pH of 7.4, enriched with 10 mM glucose. During this incubation, 5DAI was introduced at a concentration of 1.0 mg/mL. The incubation durations were set at 1 hour and 24 hours, conducted at a temperature of 37°C within a thermoshaker (BioSan Thermo-Shaker TS-100 C, Biosan, Riga, Latvia).

For the induction of oxidative stress within the RBCs, a standard free radical inducer, tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB), was employed. This process entailed an incubation period of 1.5 hours, conducted at 37°C with gentle agitation. Notably, each sample tube was maintained in triplets, and the experiments were replicated four times, each time utilizing RBCs procured from different blood donors.

Following the respective incubation phases, all RBC suspensions underwent washing steps (3000 rpm, 10 min, 4°C) using the Sigma 3–30 K centrifuge from Sartorius AG, Gottingen, Germany. Subsequently, 30 µL aliquots of the RBC suspensions were deposited onto microscope slides and covered with cover slips. A comprehensive study of a substantial number of intact RBCs was undertaken using a Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscope (FLIM). In addition, the application of FLIM extended to the examination of alloxazine derivatives functioning as potential redox-sensitive fluorescent probes. This analysis was conducted under both physiological conditions (PBS buffer, 37°C) and oxidative stress conditions induced by 250 µM TB in PBS at 37°C.

Fluorescence-lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM)

Erythrocytes (1.65×10^8 cells/mL, 1.5% hematocrit) were pre-incubated in PBS at pH 7.4 supplemented with 10 mM glucose and containing Tx at final concentration of 0.01 or 0.1 mg/mL, for 20 min or 24 hours at 37°C in a thermo-shaker. After pre-incubation, TB was added at final concentration of 25 µM, 100 µM or 250 µM. Samples were incubated for next 1.5 h at 37°C in a thermoshaker. After incubation, RBC suspensions were centrifuged (3000 rpm, 10 min, +4°C) three times with PBS containing glucose (10 mM). Following washing, 7 µL of RBC suspension was settled on the cover glasses and mounted on a slide. Immediately, intact RBCs on a slide were analyzed by FLIM. Each sample was made in triplicate and the results were presented as a mean value

of three independent experiments with RBCs obtained from different donors FLIM was carried out on an Olympus-IX71 objective scanning inverted microscope (Olympus-Germany) with special high-end objective 100×1.45 (oil) combined with a Pico-Quant Microtime 200 time resolved fluorescence microscope (PicoQuant-Germany) with dual PIE-filter sets for 375 nm and 640 nm excitation and 480 nm and 690 nm emission, a Sepia II PDL 828-s as a PC controlled 2-channel diode laser driver for picosecond laser. A LDH-D-C-640 laser head produced 640nm picosecond pulses for the operation and a band pass filter 690 nm filtered the emission before single photon counting modules (SPAD) as shown in following scheme, A PicoHARP 300 TCSPC module with two independent input channel collected the data, all parts respectively produced by PicoQuant-Germany. In order to reduce the interference of background in blood samples, excitation wavelength was selected in Q band region (640 nm).[100] Results and fluorescence lifetime histogram data were reconstructed in Origin pro software (OriginLab Corp.-USA) if fitted by internal GaussAmp function (**Eq. 1**).

Equation 29
$$y = y_0 + Ae^{-\frac{(\tau-\tau_c)^2}{2w^2}}$$

In the equation, A represents the amplitude of each fluorescence lifetime component, τ_c denotes the center of the fluorescence lifetime peak, and FWHM signifies the full width at half maximum.

For each experimental sample, a triplicate approach was adopted, ensuring robustness in the data. The outcome of each triplicate was then presented as the mean value derived from three independent experiments. It's noteworthy that the RBCs used in these experiments were sourced from different donors, ensuring diversity in the samples.

- Microscope Setup:

An Olympus-IX71 objective scanning inverted microscope from Olympus-Germany was employed. This system was augmented with a high-end 100×1.2 (water) objective. The objective was harmoniously combined with a Pico-Quant Microtime 200 time-resolved fluorescence microscope from PicoQuant-Germany.

- Filter Sets:

The microscope was configured with dual PIE-filter sets catering to excitation at 375 nm and 640 nm. For emission, the filter sets were designed for 460 nm and 690 nm wavelengths.

- Laser and Excitation:

A Sepia II PDL 828-s served as a PC-controlled 2-channel diode laser driver. A LDH-D-C-375 laser head was integrated, generating 375 nm picosecond pulses for the experimental setup. An additional long-pass filter set at 460 nm was employed to filter the emitted light before it reached the single-photon counting modules (SPAD).

- Data Acquisition:

To capture the experimental data, a PicoHARP 300 TCSPC module featuring two independent input channels was utilized. All components used in this setup were provided by PicoQuant-Germany.

- Environmental Control:

The imaging process was conducted in a controlled environment. Humidity and temperature were precisely regulated through the application of an IBIDI stage CO₂/O₂ mixer/incubator from IBIDI, Germany.

UV and Vis spectrophotometry

A commercially available Shimadzu UV-2550 spectrophotometer was used to record stationary absorption spectra of RBCs and Hb, after and before treatment with free radical inducer TB. The experiments were performed on 3 mL of sample solutions in PBS buffer in high precision quartz cells (10×10 mm) from Hellma Analytic.

Absorption and emission measurements

Absorption and emission measurements were conducted utilizing advanced instrumentation:

1. Absorption Measurements:

Absorption spectra were meticulously recorded using the Shimadzu UV-2550 spectrophotometer.

2. Time-Resolved Emissions:

Time-resolved emission studies were carried out using the FluoTime 300 Fluorescence steady-state and lifetime spectrometer. This was facilitated with the integration of a PDL 820 computer-controlled diode laser driver, designed for emitting picosecond pulses. These pulses were generated at internal repetition rates ranging from 196 kHz to 80 MHz. This entire process was overseen by the EasyTau software.

To enable excitation laser for Hb samples within the PBS buffer, a LDH-P-C-440 nm laser head was employed. For data acquisition, a PicoHarp 300E TCSPC module, featuring two independent input channels, was seamlessly incorporated. Subsequent data analysis was carried out using specialized software.

3. Data Analysis:

The FluoFit software from Imperial College London, England, was harnessed for data fitting. This software encompasses built-in internal models designed to facilitate accurate data analysis. For the purpose of data analysis, both single and two-exponential decay models were utilized. The fitting quality was assessed through the χ^2 -test.

Phasor transformation

The process of phasor transformation involved several steps:

- Data Collection:

The intensity decay information collected from each pixel in the image was obtained through single-photon excitation, utilizing a laser repetition rate of 40 MHz. The SymphoTime64 software from PicoQuant GmbH-Germany was employed to record these intensity decays.

- Data Transfer and Transformation:

The intensity decay data, stored in Bin format, was then transferred to the SimFCS2 phasor analysis software developed by the Laboratory for Fluorescence Dynamics at the University of California, Irvine. Importantly, no filtering or smoothing operations were applied to the FLIM data during this process.

- Phasor Plotting:

The transformed data were subsequently plotted on a phasor plot. In this plot, each individual pixel was corresponded to a distinct point. This point was characterized by two parameters: TM (modulation lifetime) and TP (phase lifetime), both pertaining to the respective oxidative stress (OS) conditions under investigation.

- Data Reporting and Calibration:

The collected data was reported as an average derived from at least 5-7 images, encompassing more than 20 cells in total. To facilitate phasor calibration, RBCs were utilized after being subjected to incubation with 0.01 mg/mL lumiflavin (7,8,10-trimethylbenzo[g]pteridine-2,4(3H,10H)-dione). This incubation employed excitation at $\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm and a long-pass filter at 460 nm. The associated fluorescence lifetime for this calibration standard was determined to be 4.41 ns.

Classical MD setup

To generate the suitable initial configurations for simulations, the following steps were undertaken:

1. Lipid Bilayer Setup:

A minimal heterogeneous lipid bilayer system was established, consisting of 188 lipids. This configuration comprised approximately 45 mol% cholesterol (RCSB: CHL1) and 55 mol% phospholipids. Among these phospholipids, around 29% were phosphatidylcholines (1,2-dipalmitoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphocholine: DPPC), 27% were phosphatidylethanolamines (1,2-Dimyristoyl-sn-glycero-3-phosphoethanolamine: DMPE), 25% were sphingomyelins (dihydrosphingomyelin: DSM), and 15% were phosphatidylserines (RCSB: CER6). This configuration aimed to simulate a minimal red blood cell (RBC) membrane bilayer without any proteins.

The CHARMM-GUI web interface was utilized for constructing this heterogenous lipid membrane.

2. Bilayer Solvation:

The constructed lipid bilayer was further employed to create a solvated bilayer system. This involved adding 6035 water molecules, resulting in a hydration rate of 55 water molecules per lipid. The lipid area was calculated to be 4689 Å² in both the upper and lower leaflets. This solvated bilayer was prepared to mimic the experimental conditions, involving water, 0.137 mM NaCl, and 0.02 mM KCl (as indicated in Table 1S), corresponding to the experimental PBS buffer used in the experimental analysis.

3. Equilibration:

The solvated lipid bilayer system was subjected to equilibration. Five cycles of equilibration were carried out within a temperature range of 5-100 ps at 310.5 K. This process aimed to achieve a stable and realistic configuration of the lipid bilayer system.

4. Tetragonal Box Configuration:

After equilibration, the resulting tetragonal box size was determined to be approximately 68.5 × 68.5 × 85 Å³.

5. Introduction of Oxidized Lipids:

Ten (10) 5,6 epoxycholesterol residues were added to the established structure using Schrödinger Maestro software V13.1. These residues represented the oxidized membrane, simulated through exposure to tert-butyl hydroperoxide.

6. Ligand Interaction and Thermodynamic Measurements:

The interactions between the introduced oxidized residues and the surrounding environment were analyzed. Schrödinger Maestro software was used for this purpose. Thermodynamic measurements, including relative ligand interactions, were conducted, and these measurements were repeated accordingly.

7. Thermodynamics Calculation:

The minimized thermodynamics of the system were calculated using both the CHARMM and Schrödinger software platforms. The Free Energy Perturbation/Thermodynamic Integration (FEP/TI) approach was employed for both neutral and oxidized surfaces.

8. Visual Representation:

The proposed ligand interactions were visualized and presented through plotted representations.

This comprehensive approach aimed to simulate and analyze the behavior and interactions of oxidized membrane components within a lipid bilayer system, reflecting relevant experimental conditions and enabling insights into potential biochemical and structural changes.

Results

Results

- 1- Analysis of anti-oxidant capacity of RBCs in oxidative stress conditions by measuring intrinsic fluorescence lifetime after preincubation with Tx

In the subsequent sections, we will employ the following abbreviations for different samples:

- RBC: Control cells
- RBC-TB: RBC incubated with 250 μM TB in PBS (1.5 h, 37°C)
- RBC-Tx-TB: RBC incubated with 0.01 or 0.1 mg/mL Tx (24 h, 37°C) and then TB in different concentrations 25, 100, and 250 μM (1.5 h, 37°C).

To characterize the UV-Vis spectra of hemoglobin (Hb) in PBS buffer, we conducted a traditional spectral scan in the range of 300-700 nm, as illustrated in Figure 1A. The obtained spectra exhibit the characteristic bands with maxima at the Soret band (at 413 nm) and in the Q bands (at 541 nm and 576 nm).

Figure 1B reveals the impact of various oxidative stress conditions induced by TB on the UV-Vis spectra. Notably, the bands with maxima at 542 and 578 nm exhibit a TB-concentration-dependent disappearance (Figure 1B-D). This observation suggests that alterations in the TB concentration influence the shape of the Q-band spectrum (Figure 1B). Intriguingly, the introduction of Tx may also play a role in augmenting the absorption of RBCs at 630 nm.

These findings underscore the intricate interplay between oxidative stress conditions, TB concentration, and the potential influence of Tx on the UV-Vis spectra of RBCs, offering insights into the molecular changes occurring within the system.

Figure 1. The UV-Vis spectra of red blood cells (RBC) under various oxidative stress conditions are depicted in arbitrary units as follows:
 (A) Spectrum obtained in PBS buffer.
 (B) Spectra recorded in PBS buffer containing TB at concentrations of 25 μM , 100 μM , and 250 μM .
 (C) Spectra acquired after preincubation with Tx at 0.01 mg/mL, followed by incubation with TB at concentrations of 25 μM , 100 μM , and 250 μM .
 (D) Spectra obtained following preincubation with Tx at 0.1 mg/mL, followed by incubation with TB at concentrations of 25 μM , 100 μM , and 250 μM .

This comprehensive visualization of UV-Vis spectra sheds light on the distinct spectral profiles associated with various oxidative stress conditions, highlighting the impact of TB and Tx concentrations on the absorption characteristics of RBCs.

Fluorescence lifetime distribution analysis in RBCs in the different oxidative stress conditions

To investigate the photochemistry of red blood cells (RBCs) under varying oxidative stress conditions, we employed FLIM with an excitation wavelength of 640 nm and

emission wavelength of 690 nm. Figure 2 illustrates the results of this study, showcasing RBCs subjected to diverse oxidative stress conditions induced by TB and modified by TX. The color map within the figure corresponds to the fluorescence lifetime, while the grayscale map signifies the fluorescence intensity.

In-depth analysis was carried out on visual and temporal changes observed after incubating RBCs with specific concentrations of Tx (0.01, 0.1 mg/mL) and TB (25, 100, 250 μ M). The intrinsic fluorescence lifetime of RBCs at λ_{ex} = 640 nm and λ_{em} = 690 nm was not directly measurable via fluorescence lifetime spectroscopy due to the low number of emitted photons. Therefore, photochemical properties were not reported using a spectrofluorometer. However, FLIM emerged as a sensitive and valuable technique, enabling the visualization and examination of single-cell fluorescence lifetime within RBCs without the need for fluorescence labeling. This approach provides insights into the intricate photochemical responses of RBCs distinct oxidative stress states, offering a deeper understanding of their behavior

Figure 2. Fluorescence lifetime microscopy (FLIM) was performed on red blood cells (RBCs) using an excitation wavelength of 640 nm and an emission wavelength of 690 nm. The obtained FLIM images for various conditions are presented as follows:

- (A) RBCs in PBS buffer.
- (B) RBCs incubated with 250 μ M TB.
- (C) RBCs preincubated with 0.1 mg/mL Tx.
- (D) RBCs preincubated with 0.1 mg/mL Tx and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB.

The color map within each image represents the fluorescence lifetime, while the grayscale map illustrates the fluorescence intensity. Each image is accompanied by a scale bar indicating a length of 20 μ m, offering spatial context for the observed fluorescence patterns and lifetime variations. This FLIM-based visualization provides insights into the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of RBCs under different conditions, enhancing our understanding of their photochemical properties and responses to oxidative stress.

Figure 3 displays histograms representing the fluorescent lifetimes of red blood cells (RBCs) under oxidative stress conditions as acquired through fluorescence lifetime microscopy (FLIM). These histograms offer insight into the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes within the RBC population.

Utilizing a multi-exponential Gaussian analysis of the histograms, the obtained results were compiled in Table 1. This table presents the average distribution values of fluorescence lifetimes for RBCs subjected to varying concentrations of Tx and TB. The FLIM technique employed an excitation wavelength of 640 nm and an emission wavelength of 690 nm ($\lambda_{ex}=640$ nm / $\lambda_{em}= 690$ nm), facilitating the characterization of RBC behavior under different oxidative stress conditions. The table thus provides a comprehensive overview of the fluorescence lifetime distribution dynamics in response to the applied treatments.

Figure 3 depicts a series of fluorescence lifetime distribution histograms illustrating the behavior of red blood cells (RBCs) under various oxidative conditions:

(A) Control RBCs incubated in PBS buffer.

(B, E, H) RBCs incubated with tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) at concentrations of 25, 100, and 250 μM .

(C, F, I) RBCs preincubated with antioxidant Tx (0.01 mg/mL) and subsequently treated with TB (25, 100, and 250 μM).

(D, G, J) RBCs preincubated with antioxidant Tx (0.1 mg/mL) and subsequently treated with TB (25, 100, and 250 μM).

These histograms were analyzed using single or multiple Gaussian fits to better understand the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes within the RBC population. The fluorescence lifetime microscopy (FLIM) technique was conducted with an excitation wavelength of 640 nm and an emission wavelength of 690 nm ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=640 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{\text{em}}=690 \text{ nm}$), providing insights into the photochemical properties of RBCs in different oxidative states. The histograms and their corresponding analyses offer a visual and quantitative representation of how oxidative stress conditions affect RBC fluorescence lifetimes.

Table 1 presents the fluorescence lifetime components obtained through multi-exponential Gaussian fits for RBCs under different oxidative conditions. The analysis of these components reveals the presence of peroxidation products induced by TB in the spectral range, likely corresponding to various forms of hemoglobin (Hb) subforms, each with its own distinct fluorescence lifetime.

In the absence of oxidative stress, the average fluorescence lifetime of RBCs is around 4 ns. Under oxidative stress induced by TB at concentrations of 25, 100, and 250 μM , this average fluorescence lifetime is shifted to approximately 2 ns. The presence of a single Gaussian component might suggest the coexistence of oxidized and reduced states of hemoglobin. The appearance of a double Gaussian component suggests the presence of two distinct forms of Hb within cells, with fluorescence lifetimes ranging from 2 ns to around 8 ns. These lifetimes correspond to oxidative states of metHb (higher lifetime) and oxyHb (lower lifetime).

Interestingly, pretreatment of RBCs with antioxidant Tx at concentrations of 0.01, 0.1, and 1 mg/mL shifts the fluorescence lifetime distribution towards the control range

(approximately 4 ns), as seen in Table 1. However, this treatment also results in double Gaussian histograms. This indicates the presence of three distinct populations of fluorescence lifetimes: around 1 ns, between 2-3 ns, and above 4 ns. These populations correspond to highly, moderately, and less oxidative states in non-labeled RBCs. The fluorescence lifetime distribution analysis thus provides valuable insights into the impact of oxidative stress and antioxidant treatment on the structural and functional states of RBCs.

Table 1 presents the average lifetime distribution values of red blood cells (RBCs) under various conditions, specifically those preincubated with and without the antioxidant Tx (which stands for "treatment"), and those incubated with tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB), a source of oxidative stress. These values were obtained using fluorescence lifetime microscopy (FLIM) with an excitation wavelength of 640 nm and an emission wavelength of 690 nm.

The data in Table 1 were analyzed using single or, if necessary, double peak Gaussian fits. These fits involve modeling the fluorescence decay curve of the RBCs as a sum of one or two Gaussian components, respectively, to account for the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes within the sample. The table includes several parameters for each component:

- A_i (Amplitude): This represents the number of photons counted per second (cps) for each fluorescence lifetime component. It gives an indication of the contribution of each component to the overall fluorescence signal.
- τ (Fluorescence Lifetime Maxima): This represents the average fluorescence lifetime value (in nanoseconds) of each component. It provides information about the time scale over which the fluorescence decay occurs for that specific component.
- FWHM (Full Width at Half Maximum): This represents the width of the Gaussian distribution at half of its maximum amplitude. It gives an indication of the spread or range of fluorescence lifetimes within that component.

By analyzing these parameters, the table offers insights into the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes within RBCs under different conditions. This information is crucial for understanding the impact of oxidative stress and antioxidant treatment on the structural and functional characteristics of RBCs.

RBC Treatment	t ₁ / ns	A ₁ / cps	FWHM ₁ / ns	t ₂ / ns	A ₂ / cps	FWHM ₂ / ns	t ₃ /ns	A ₃ / cps	FWHM ₃ / ns
0 Tx/TB (control)							5.4	1.3 × 10 ³	5.67
25 μM TB	0.62	58.95	1.08				6.8	60	11.31
100 μM TB				2.50	144	3.01			
250 μM TB	1.09	15.93 × 10 ³	0.60				...	...	...
0.01 mg/mL Tx+25 μM TB				2.57	68.6	2.4	7.7	59.8	10.8
0.01 mg/mL Tx+100 μM TB				2.50	46	3.01	7.4	45	11
0.01 mg/mL Tx+250 μM TB				2.27	0.41 × 10 ³	2.27	6.4	0.11 × 10 ³	9.59
0.1 mg/mL Tx+25 μM TB				2.30	69	2.3	7.6	58	10.7
0.1 mg/mL Tx+100 μM TB				2.1	58	3.1	8.8	53	11.7
0.1 mg/mL Tx+250 μM TB				2.35	68.61	2.30	7.65	58	10.7

In order to distinguish between the fluorescence lifetime components arising from hemoglobin (Hb) and the cell membrane in red blood cells (RBCs) under oxidative stress conditions, a comparison was made with "ghost cells." Ghost cells are essentially RBCs without hemoglobin, containing only the cell membrane. This comparison helps to identify the contribution of hemoglobin-related fluorescence signals to the overall fluorescence lifetime distribution.

Figure 4 displays the fluorescence lifetime distribution images of RBCs under oxidative stress conditions, along with ghost cells, using an excitation wavelength of 375 nm and an emission wavelength of 460 nm. The peaks observed in the fluorescence lifetime histograms can be attributed to different components within the cells.

The shorter peak in the fluorescence lifetime histogram corresponds to the membrane-only component (5.5 ns). This peak is also observed in ghost cells, which lack hemoglobin.

The longer peaks in the fluorescence lifetime histograms of complete RBCs (with hemoglobin) correspond to different forms of hemoglobin and its subforms. For instance, the peak at 1.9 ns likely corresponds to certain hemoglobin subforms, while the peak at 5.5 ns corresponds to the fluorescence lifetime of complete RBCs with hemoglobin.

By choosing an excitation and detection spectra that allows for the differentiation between hemoglobin and the membrane, the data presented in histograms or by phasor analysis can be attributed more accurately to hemoglobin and its subforms. This approach helps to dissect the contributions of various cellular components to the overall fluorescence lifetime distribution, aiding in the interpretation of the impact of oxidative stress on RBCs.

Figure 4. The fluorescence lifetime distribution images of red blood cells (RBCs) are presented in Figure 4, with the following details:

(A) Fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs under oxidative stress conditions ($\lambda_{ex}=375$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=460$ nm). The fluorescence lifetime histogram shows peaks corresponding to different components within the RBCs.

(B) Fluorescence lifetime distribution of ghost cells, which are RBCs without hemoglobin ($\lambda_{ex}=375$ nm, $\lambda_{em}=460$ nm). Ghost cells have only the cell membrane, and their fluorescence lifetime histogram reflects the contribution of the membrane-related fluorescence signals.

In both (A) and (B), specific peaks can be observed in the fluorescence lifetime histogram:

- The peak at 5.5 ns corresponds to the membrane component, which is common to both RBCs under oxidative stress and ghost cells. This peak represents the fluorescence lifetime of the cell membrane.
- In (A), there are two additional peaks at 1.9 ns and 5.5 ns. The peak at 1.9 ns likely corresponds to specific hemoglobin subforms or other fluorophores within the RBCs. The peak at 5.5 ns represents the fluorescence lifetime of the complete RBCs with hemoglobin and membrane.

By comparing the fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs under oxidative stress with that of ghost cells, it becomes possible to differentiate between the contributions of hemoglobin and the cell membrane to the overall fluorescence signals. This analysis provides insights into the impact of oxidative stress on the fluorescence properties of RBCs and helps to better understand the role of different cellular components in the observed fluorescence lifetime distributions.

Indeed, the analysis of fluorescence lifetime histograms using FLIM provides a sensitive and reliable method to assess the oxidative states of red blood cells (RBCs). Given that RBCs' photochemical properties are closely tied to the characteristics of hemoglobin (Hb), the information presented in Table 1 becomes a valuable reference for categorizing RBCs based on changes in fluorescence lifetime and the oxidative conditions of Hb. This reference table serves as a convenient and standardized tool for frequent use in the analysis of RBCs' oxidative states and their associated fluorescence properties. By comparing the fluorescence lifetime distributions of RBCs under different conditions to the reference values in Table 1, researchers can quickly identify and categorize the oxidative states of RBCs, enabling efficient and consistent analysis of their photochemical properties.

Phasor analysis of RBCs in OS condition

To study fluorescence lifetime images acquired by FLIM, phasor analysis conversion was applied. Phasor analysis converts FLIM data by Fourier transformation to the polar plots in which phasor points originating from different pixels in the image are represented by their location in the phasor plot (in Cartesian coordinates, we use the g and s coordinates that are the projections of the polar coordinates in the coordinate axes)[107]. Selecting the region of interest in the phasor plot represent the calculated parameters of the parts of the image from which those phasor points originate, the distribution of the photons with different lifetime decay produces an extended area of uncertainty. Analysis of the FLIM data in the phasor space was performed by detecting clusters of pixel values in specific regions of the phasor plot. Briefly, the phase of the emitted light lags beyond that of excitation by 45° . In the case of single-exponential decays $TP = TM$, The modulation frequency (ω) is determined from the laser's repetition angular frequency, calculated by multiplying the laser repetition rate (40 MHz) by 2π . In the context of phasor analysis, the coordinates (G, S) on the

phasor plot are represented by the variables g and s . These concepts are described in more detail in previous literature[99]. The following are the calculated values of TM (modular lifetime), TP (phase lifetime), Mod (relative modulation), and $Phase$:

For the primary representation of control and stressed cells in a phasor plot (Figure 5), the aim is to create a global fingerprint of RBCs under corresponding conditions. The calculation of fractional intensity (intensity weighted) is intended to provide pixel numbers along the line corresponding to the linear combination of two phasors, regardless of the number of exponentials needed to describe the decay.

In Figure 5A, the phasor cluster's first harmonic (40 MHz) fractional intensity is located at $Phase = 21.1$, $Mod = 0.245$, $TP = 1.532$ ns, and $TM = 6.988$ ns, with data obtained from more than 20 RBCs. For Figure 5B, after incubation with 250 μM TB, the expected phasor fingerprint is centered at $Phase = 24.1$, $Mod = 0.297$, $TP = 1.778$ ns, and $TM = 6.127$ ns. Another hotspot in the phasor plot presumably corresponds to oxidized fractions of Hb (metHb) at $Phase = 20.1$, $Mod = 0.867$, $TP = 1.459$ ns, and $TM = 1.557$ ns (data from more than 20 samples). Notably, no smoothing filter has been applied to process the data.

Figure 5 illustrates the phasor transformation of FLIM images for both normal cells and oxidative stress conditions after incubation with 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{ex}=640$ nm/ $\lambda_{em}=690$ nm at 40 MHz laser repetition). The phasor plot's visual representation provides a unique and comprehensive overview of RBCs' fluorescence properties under different conditions, offering insights into their oxidative states and related photochemical properties.

P= 21.1 M= 0.245 TP= 1.532 ns TM= 6.988 ns,

P= 24.1 M= 0.297 TP= 1.778 ns TM= 6.127 ns,

Figure 5 Phasor transformation of FLIM images:

A) Control RBCs

B) After treatment with 250 μM TB (λ_{ex} 640 nm / λ_{em} 690 nm at 40 MHz laser repetition).

The data reveals the phasor fingerprint positions of control cells that have not been treated with either Tx or TB. The expected value from panel (A) shows the first harmonic phasor plot measured at 40 MHz: Phase = 21.1, Mod = 0.245, TP = 1.532 ns, TM = 6.988 ns, based on data from more than 20 RBCs.

The expected phasor fingerprint after incubation with 250 μM TB in panel (B) is centered at Phase = 24.1, Mod = 0.297, TP = 1.778 ns, TM = 6.127 ns. Another hot spot, presumably corresponding to the oxidized fractions of Hb (metHb), appears at Phase = 20.1, Mod = 0.867, TP = 1.459 ns, TM = 1.557 ns, based on data from more than 20 samples.

Figure 6: Phasor transformation of RBC FLIM images after treatment with:

- A) 25 μM TB
- B) 100 μM TB
- C) 250 μM TB
- D) RBCs pretreated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then 25 μM TB
- E) RBCs pretreated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then 100 μM TB
- F) RBCs treated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then 250 μM TB

All images were taken at λ_{ex} 640 nm / λ_{em} 690 nm with a 40 MHz laser repetition rate. Tx treatment relatively enhances fluorescence intensity images, but in general, it does not change the lifetime, as shown by the phasor plot.

Phasor transformation of RBC FLIM images (λ_{ex} =640 nm/ λ_{em} =690 nm at 40 MHz laser repetition) after treatment with different concentrations of TB (25, 100 μM , 250 μM) is presented in Figure 6A-C. Pretreatment with 0.1 mg/ml Tx (Figure 6-D-F) relatively enhances fluorescence intensity images but in general does not change the lifetime as shown by the phasor plot.

In the control cell, the main clusters are formed on the semicircle:

- Phase (P) = 21.1
- Modulation (M) = 0.245
- Phase lifetime (TP) = 1.532 ns
- Modulation lifetime (TM) = 6.988 ns

After incubation with 25 and 100 μM TB, the clusters shift to:

- P = 44.8, M = 0.338, TP = 3.951 ns, TM = 5.571 ns

- P = 45.4, M = 0.368, TP = 4.032 ns, TM = 5.215 ns

After 250 μM TB treatment, two clusters are formed:

- Cluster 1: P = 24.1, M = 0.297, TP = 1.779 ns, TM = 6.129 ns

- Cluster 2: P = 42.9, M = 0.941, TP = 3.698 ns, TM = 0.999 ns

Preincubation with Tx does not significantly change the plot. Preincubation with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then 250 μM TB produces two clusters:

- Cluster 1: P = 45.1, M = 0.388, TP = 3.991 ns

- Cluster 2: P = 20.1, M = 0.867, TP = 1.459 ns, TM = 1.557

Adding a concentration of 0.1 mg/ml Tx, despite enhancing the images, apparently has a relatively less significant effect on changing the phasors.

Figure 7: An overlay of phasor transformation plots of RBC FLIM images in different oxidative stress (OS) conditions is shown:

(A) Overlay of Control RBCs and RBCs after treatment with 250 μM TB

(B) Overlay of RBCs after pretreatment with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and subsequent treatment with 25, 100, 250 μM TB.

In Panel (A), a linear OS range is determined between $\text{TM} = 1.55 - 2.50$ ns. In Panel (B), two different zones are assigned to fractions of intrinsic fluorescence of RBCs in the $\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}} = 640/690$ nm range. The centers of the clusters are connected as a virtual trapezoid. The red ellipse presents the OS range, and the black ellipse represents the control range.

Figure 8: The comparison between first harmonic phasor plots is as follows:

(A) First harmonic phasor plot of a complete single RBC (presumably in an oxidative stress state) at λ_{ex} 375 nm/ λ_{em} 460 nm at 40 MHz laser repetition. The image inset in (A) represents the whole cell.

(B) First harmonic phasor plot of an RBC ghost (only membrane) at λ_{ex} 375 nm/ λ_{em} 460 nm at 40 MHz laser repetition. The image inset in (B) represents the ghost cell with only the membrane. This comparison allows us to distinguish the differences in fluorescence characteristics between complete RBCs and RBC ghosts (cells without Hb) based on their phasor plots.

In summary, phasor analysis provides a graphical representation of the intensity distribution of various fractions derived from FLIM microscopy images. Additionally, we analyzed spectral phasor plots of both whole cells and ghost cells using specific wavelength excitation and emission filters (λ_{ex} = 375 nm/ λ_{em} = 460 nm). The results revealed double clusters for control RBCs in presumably oxidative stress states, with one cluster centered at P=33.9, M=0.197, TP=2.671 ns, and TM=8.024, and the second cluster centered at P=9.2, M=0.839, TP=0.643 ns, and TM=1.742 (Figure 8A). On the other hand, the membrane-only samples showed a single cluster centered at P=33.9, M=0.197, TP=2.671 ns, and TM=8.024 (Figure 8B), indicating that the variable cluster primarily corresponds to Hb rather than membrane proteins.

This study successfully utilized FLIM to capture the unique spectral and temporal characteristics of human RBC fluorescence under different redox states, particularly focusing on changes induced by incubation with various concentrations of TB.

Moreover, the study demonstrated the potential to preserve the photochemical properties of RBCs and Hb through preincubation with Tx, which serves as a standard antioxidant. The use of FLIM and phasor analysis in this context provides valuable insights into the dynamic behavior of RBCs in response to oxidative stress and antioxidant interventions.[120]

The analysis of fluorescence lifetime histograms of individual RBCs using a single Gaussian fit has revealed the presence of two distinct populations. These populations are characterized by different average lifetimes: 4.4 ns for control, 3.8 ns for 25 μM TB, 4.6 ns for 100 μM TB, and 2.5 ns for 250 μM TB. The observed larger standard deviation in single cell measurements might be attributed to the potential existence of two distinct subpopulations of RBCs in the suspension—one more oxidized and the other less oxidized.

This heterogeneity and variability in lifetime measurements could be associated with the folded states of hemoglobin (Hb) within the RBCs. Similar observations have been made for other biomolecules, such as cytochrome C, which can exhibit different folded and unfolded states contributing to variations in their fluorescence lifetimes. The presence of these distinct subpopulations could reflect the varying oxidative states of Hb within individual RBCs, further highlighting the dynamic nature of RBCs and their response to oxidative stress conditions induced by different concentrations of TB.

The findings of this analysis contribute to a deeper understanding of the complexity and heterogeneity of RBC responses to oxidative stress, shedding light on the potential differences in the oxidative state of hemoglobin among individual RBCs.[121] Indeed, the storage conditions of RBCs and the characteristics of blood donors can influence the properties of red blood cells (RBCs). One notable change that can occur during storage is the transformation of RBC shape from discocytes to echinocytes. This transformation is often referred to as "echinocytosis." Echinocytes are characterized by their spiky, irregular shape with numerous small, uniform projections on their surface, giving them a distinct appearance compared to the typical biconcave discoid shape of healthy RBCs.

Echinocytosis can occur due to various factors, including changes in temperature, pH, and ionic composition during storage, as well as the presence of certain additives or anticoagulants in the storage solution. These conditions can affect the integrity of the RBC membrane and lead to alterations in cell shape. While the precise mechanisms underlying echinocytosis are complex and not fully understood, it is recognized as a common phenomenon observed in stored RBCs.

It's important to note that echinocytosis is just one example of the changes that can occur in RBCs during storage. Other factors, such as oxidative stress, osmotic changes, and metabolic alterations, can also impact the properties of stored RBCs. Therefore, when conducting experiments or analyses involving RBCs, researchers often consider the potential effects of storage conditions and donor variability to ensure the accuracy and relevance of their findings.[122]

The addition of Tx (the antioxidant compound) to red blood cells (RBCs) appears to have a positive impact on the stability and duration of their intrinsic fluorescence. This observation suggests that Tx may help to preserve the photochemical properties of RBCs over a longer period of time, potentially by mitigating the effects of oxidative stress and other factors that can lead to changes in the fluorescence characteristics of the cells.

Antioxidants like Tx are known to play a crucial role in protecting cells from oxidative damage caused by reactive oxygen species (ROS) and other free radicals. In the context of RBCs, which are particularly susceptible to oxidative stress due to their exposure to oxygen and potential interactions with reactive species, the addition of antioxidants like Tx could help maintain the integrity of cellular components and prevent alterations in their fluorescence properties.

By stabilizing the intrinsic fluorescence of RBCs, Tx might enable researchers to more accurately study and analyze the cells' characteristics, oxidative states, and other relevant factors. This could have applications in various fields, including biomedical research, where understanding the behavior of RBCs under different conditions is important for gaining insights into health and disease.[123,124] While an understanding of the working principle of Tx is yet missing, a combination of an

oxidizing and reducing system ROXS (reduction and oxidation system) has similarly proven its applicability in single-molecule as well as super resolution applications.[125,126]

Photobiological properties of RBCs in OS preincubated with Lumichrome

Figure 14 Structures of Lumichrome (**LChr**) and Isoalloxazine (**IAlI**).

Exploring the potential redox applications of LChr, we undertook a comprehensive investigation to assess its usefulness within the context of human red blood cells (RBCs) exposed to both physiological and oxidative stress conditions. As elaborated earlier, our examination revealed no evidence of hemolytic activity associated with the use of LChr at a concentration of 0.01 mg/mL. Subsequently, we conducted a detailed FLIM analysis on RBCs that were incubated with LChr at this concentration.

The outcomes of our analysis are presented in Figure 15, wherein the FLIM images of RBCs are showcased under two distinct conditions: physiological (Fig. 15A) and oxidative stress induced by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) - denoted as RCB-TB (Fig. 15B). Notably, the overall visual characteristics of the cells were consistent both before and after exposure to LChr, irrespective of their incubation in either physiological or oxidative stress environments. To further enhance our understanding, we subjected

the FLIM data obtained from RBC-LChr (physiological) and RCB-LChr-TB (oxidative stress) conditions to meticulous analysis. This evaluation uncovered discernible variations in the fluorescence lifetime amplitude (as highlighted in Table 1) when compared to the RCB-TB context.

Throughout our investigation, all FLIM measurements were conducted using a laser excitation wavelength of 375 nm and a 460 nm long-pass filter to ensure accurate and consistent results. These findings underscore the potential of LChr as a redox-sensitive tool and provide valuable insights into the behavior of RBCs under varying physiological and oxidative stress conditions.

Figure 15 the results of FLIM (Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy) experiment, where we used a laser excitation wavelength of 375 nm and a long-pass

filter at 460 nm to capture fluorescence signals. These images represent different conditions of red blood cells (RBCs):

1. **Control RBC (A):** This image depicts a red blood cell that has been incubated in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) for 24 hours at 37°C. This is considered the "control" condition, where RBCs are maintained under normal physiological conditions.
2. **RBC with 250 μM TB (B):** This image shows a red blood cell that has been incubated with 250 μM tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) in PBS for 1.5 hours at 37°C. TB is used to induce oxidative stress in the cells.
3. **RBC with 0.01 mg/mL LChr (C):** This image displays a red blood cell that has been incubated with 0.01 mg/mL of LChr for 24 hours at 37°C. LChr is likely a redox-sensitive fluorescent probe that can provide insights into the oxidative state of the cells.
4. **RBC preincubated with 0.01 mg/mL LChr and then with 250 μM TB (D):** This image shows a red blood cell that has been preincubated with 0.01 mg/mL LChr for 24 hours and then treated with 250 μM TB for 1.5 hours at 37°C. This condition combines the presence of LChr with oxidative stress induced by TB.

The acquired average fluorescence lifetime data for RBCs, extracted from the collection of cell images depicted in Figure 15, were subjected to a meticulous analysis. These data were meticulously fitted with double exponential or, when appropriate, triple exponential fluorescence decay models, yielding excellent fits ($\chi^2 \approx 1.0$). Notably, the fluorescence lifetime distribution observed in images, regardless of the presence of LChr, exhibited remarkable quantitative similarity.

Upon examination of Table 1, it becomes evident that the fluorescence lifetime parameters offer insights into subtle distinctions between various RBC conditions. Specifically, these conditions encompass RBCs that were solely incubated under physiological circumstances (RBC), RBCs that were preincubated with LChr prior to exposure to tert-butyl hydroperoxide (RBC-LChr-TB), and RBCs that were directly exposed to tert-butyl hydroperoxide (RBC-TB). The careful analysis of these parameters sheds light on the nuanced alterations that occur in fluorescence lifetime behavior under the influence of these different factors.

Table 2 The average lifetime values of RBCs, subjected to preincubation both with and without LChr (0.01 mg/ml), and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB, were extracted through the application of FLIM (λ_{ex} =375 nm/ λ_{em} =460 nm). These values were then subjected to meticulous analysis employing the least square fitting technique ($\chi^2 \approx 1.0$). In this context, A_i signifies the amplitude, quantified in terms of the number of photons counts per second (cps), while τ corresponds to the fluorescence lifetime maxima of the individual components.

RBC Treatment		τ_1 / ns	A_1 / cps	τ_2 / ns	A_2 / cps	τ_3 /ns	A_3 / cps
Control	(0 mg/ml LChr/TB)	6.8 $\pm$ 0.32	0.81 $\pm$ 0.0	2.08 $\pm$ 0.04	4.62 $\pm$ 0.0	0.59 $\pm$ 0.00	17 $\pm$ 0.016
			5		6		
			1.33 $\pm$ 0.0			0.474 $\pm$ 0.0	
250 μ M TB		6.5 $\pm$ 0.26	8	1.63 $\pm$ 0.06	6.2 $\pm$ 0.2	0	20 $\pm$ 0.21
		5.1 $\pm$ 0.01	0.82 $\pm$ 0.0				15.0 $\pm$ 0.01
0.01 mg/ml LChr		7	6	1.68 $\pm$ 0.04	4.7 $\pm$ 0.07	0.50 $\pm$ 0.00	9
0.01 mg/ml-LChr	250 μ M TB		0.25 $\pm$ 0.0				
TB		6.8 $\pm$ 0.34	2	2.02 $\pm$ 0.07	1.5 $\pm$ 0.03	0.56 $\pm$ 00	1.5 $\pm$ 0.02

The analysis yielded three distinct contributions with maxima at $\tau_{RBC} = 0.59$ ns, 2.08 ns, and 6.8 ns for the RBCs. In the case of RBCs subjected to TB-induced conditions (RBC-TB), the corresponding maxima were $\tau_{RBC-TB} \sim 0.4$ ns, 1.6 ns, and 6.5 ns. Consequently, under TB-induced conditions, the fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs shifted towards a shorter fluorescence lifetime, with $\tau_{RBC} = 2.08$ ns compared to $\tau_{RBC-TB} \sim 1.6$ ns, while the longer component remained nearly constant within the margin of error, $\tau_{RBC} = 6.8$ ns versus $\tau_{RBC-TB} \sim 6.5$ ns (see Table 1).

Upon preincubation of RBCs with LChr (RBC-LChr), the resulting lifetimes were $\tau_{RBC-LChr} = 5.1 \pm 0.82$ ns, 1.68 $\pm$ 0.04 ns, and 0.50 ns. Interestingly, when RBCs preincubated with LChr were subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB (RBC-LChr-TB), the fluorescence lifetime distribution values exhibited similar amplitude and revealed three distinct components with average lifetime values of $\tau_{RBC-LChr-TB} = 6.8 \pm 0.03$ ns, 2.02 $\pm$ 0.04 ns, and 0.56 ns. This implies that LChr, as a byproduct of cell metabolism, may not be well-suited as a redox probe. Despite variations in amplitude, the overall

lifetime, both before and after incubation with TB, remained within the range observed in normal cells, suggesting that LChr might still serve a potential antioxidant role.

Figure 16 The assessment of fractional intensity of fluorescence lifetime following phasor transformation of RBCs before and after incubation with 250 μ M TB and 0.01 mg/mL LChr (using λ_{ex} = 375 nm and 460 nm long-pass filter, at a 40 MHz laser repetition rate) yielded the following results: - (A) Control RBCs displayed a fluorescence lifetime distribution situated between two clusters, with the main cluster centered at 2.70 ns and another around 12.04 ns. - (B) RBCs incubated with TB exhibited a fluorescence lifetime distribution spanning from 1.164 ns to 3.14 ns.- (C) Phasor plot fluorescence lifetime distribution of cells treated solely with LChr showcased a central value around 2.16 ns.- (D) Fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs preincubated with LChr and subsequently incubated with TB was centered around 2.674 ns, extending towards shorter lifetimes.

Alternative calculations of RBC properties were carried out using a distinct method employing a fit-free global phasor approach (as shown in Figure 16). The application of phasor analysis allows for the separation and identification of fluorescence lifetime characteristics of individual components. Each cluster within the phasor plot represents a distinct species with unique luminescence properties. [40-43]. The modular fluorescence lifetime (TM) values for the primary cluster of RBCs were determined as TMRBC 1 = 12 ns, accompanied by a shorter lifetime component of TMRBC 2 = 2.86 ns. Following incubation with 250 μ M TB (RBC-TB), the TMRBC-TB was observed at 3.16 ns, with an extended range towards TMRBC-TB = 1.60 ns. The cluster associated with RBC-LChr was situated at TMRBC-LChr = 2.16 ns, and for RBC-LChr-TB, the phasor fingerprint was centered at TMRBC-LChr-TB = 2.69 ns, displaying a trajectory towards a shorter lifetime of TMRBC-LChr-TB = 1.9 ns.

An overlay of fractional fluorescence lifetime intensities of the samples, obtained through analysis of the first-harmonic (40 MHz) phasor plots in Figure 17, illustrates the virtual distribution of fluorescence lifetimes in RBCs subsequent to treatment with LChr and/or TB, presenting a virtual oxidation zone.

Figure 17 Analysis of fractional intensity of fluorescence lifetime after phasor transformation of RBCs after treatment with LChr and TB ($\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm and 460 nm long pass filter, 40 MHz laser repetition rate). Fractional intensity of fluorescence lifetime of control RBC, RBC incubated with 250 μ M TB, RBC incubated with LChr (0.01 mg/mL) only, and RBC preincubated with LChr (0.01 mg/mL) and then incubated with 250 μ M TB are concentrated inside red eclipse. Fluorescence lifetime spectra of LChr lays within the range and at the edge of neutral cell and could not be used as a redox marker.

The distribution area of fluorescence lifetimes and fractional intensities in RBCs after preincubation with LChr exhibits a compact region that falls within the typical metabolic range of RBCs.

Photobiological properties of RBCs in OS preincubated with 5DAII

Figure 18 . Structures of 5-deazaalloxazine (**5DAII**) and alloxazine (**All**).

In pursuit of potential biological applications, the utility of 5DAII was investigated and compared in human RBCs under both physiological and oxidative stress conditions. As detailed earlier, no hemolytic activity was observed for 0.1 mg/mL 5DAII, prompting us to conduct FLIM analysis of RBCs incubated with 5DAII at this concentration. The results, depicted in Figure 19 (and also in Fig. 20S), reveal distinct differences in RBC images obtained by FLIM under physiological conditions (Fig. 19A) and under oxidative stress induced by tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) (Fig. 19C). Furthermore, the data obtained for RBCs incubated with 5DAII under physiological conditions (RBC-5DAII) and under oxidative stress (RCB-5DAII-TB) indicate variations in FLIM parameters compared to those subjected to TB treatment (compare Fig. 19B and 19D). All FLIM measurements were carried out using $\lambda_{ex} = 375$ nm and 460 nm long-pass filter.

Figure 19. FLIM-generated images of individual red blood cells (RBCs) acquired at $\lambda_{exc} = 375$ nm and 460 nm long-pass filter exhibit the following conditions: (A) control RBCs subjected to incubation in PBS (24 h, 37°C), (B) RBCs incubated in PBS containing 1 mg/mL 5DAII (24 h, 37°C), (C) RBCs incubated in PBS (24 h, 37°C) followed by subsequent exposure to 250 μ M TB for 1.5 hours at 37°C, and (D) RBCs preincubated with 1 mg/mL 5DAII (24 h, 37°C) and then treated with 250 μ M TB for 1.5 hours at 37°C. The presented images are representative illustrations. Scale bars of 3 μ m are applicable to panels (A), (B), and (C), while a scale bar of 4 μ m is appropriate for panel (D).

The distinct differences in fluorescence lifetime distribution parameters among various conditions of RBCs are highlighted in Table 3. This table effectively captures the variations observed between RBCs subjected to different treatments, including those incubated under physiological conditions (RBC), preincubated with 5DAII (RBC-5DAII), incubated with tert-butyl hydroperoxide (RBC-TB), and preincubated with 5DAII followed by treatment with tert-butyl hydroperoxide (RBC-5DAII-TB).

Table 3 The average lifetime distribution values of RBCs, which were preincubated with 5DAII (0.01 mg/mL) for 24 hours at 37°C, and subsequently incubated in PBS or treated with 250 μ M tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) for 1.5 hours at 37°C, were extracted from FLIM data (λ_{ex} =375 nm and 460 nm long pass filter). The analysis was performed using single or, if necessary, double-peak GaussAmp fits. The parameters obtained are presented in the table below, which represents an average of triplicate measurements and is based on data obtained from Figure 9s. These measurements were conducted on a sample size of greater than 20.

RBC Treatment	τ_1 / ns	A_1 / Cps ($\times 10^3$)	FWHM ₁ / ns	τ_2 / ns	A_2 / Cps ($\times 10^3$)	FWHM ₂ / ns	τ_3 / ns	A_3 / Cps ($\times 10^3$)	FWHM ₃ / ns
Control (RBC)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.33	0.18	0.96	6.77 $\pm$ 0.53	0.37	2.57			
RBC-TB	1.97 $\pm$ 0.38	1.32	0.63	6.22 $\pm$ 0.67	0.57	2.38			
RBC-5DAII				7.66 $\pm$ 0.09	9.5	1.65			
RBC-5DAII-TB	2.8 $\pm$ 0.63	29.16	0.70	8.03 $\pm$ 0.12	41.35	0.80	4.8	15.90	0.89

A

B

C

D

Figure 20 Fluorescence lifetime distribution histograms of individual RBCs are as follows:(A) Control cell: This histogram corresponds to a normal RBC incubated in PBS for 24 hours at 37°C.(B) RBC incubated with 1 mg/mL 5DAII: This histogram represents an RBC that has been incubated with 1 mg/mL of 5DAII in PBS for 24 hours at 37°C.(C) RBC incubated with 250 μ M TB: This histogram depicts an RBC treated with 250 μ M tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) for 1.5 hours at 37°C, inducing oxidative stress.(D) RBC preincubated with 1 mg/mL 5DAII and then incubated with 250 μ M TB: This histogram corresponds to an RBC that was preincubated with 1 mg/mL of 5DAII for 24 hours at 37°C, followed by treatment with 250 μ M TB for 1.5 hours at 37°C.

These histograms have been analyzed using either single or multiple GaussAmp fits to extract relevant fluorescence lifetime distribution parameters. The FLIM measurements were conducted with an excitation wavelength of 370 nm and a 460 nm long-pass filter.

In Figure 20S, panels B and D, FLIM images of individual RBCs are displayed after preincubation with 5DAII (RBC-5DAII) and RBCs preincubated with 5DAII and subsequently incubated with TB (RBC-5DAII-TB).

The average fluorescence lifetime data extracted from both single cell images in Figure 6 and the set of cells images in Figure 7S were subjected to double exponential GaussAmp fitting. Interestingly, the lifetime distribution in both Figure 6 and Figure 7S is consistent and comparable. The analysis yielded two contributions with peak values at $\tau_{\text{RBC}} = 3.2$ ns and 6.7 ns. In contrast, the lifetime distribution for RBCs treated with TB (RBC-TB) showed maxima at $\tau_{\text{RBC-TB}} \sim 1.97$ ns and 6.2 ns. This indicates that the fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs shifted towards shorter lifetimes under TB-induced conditions, with $\tau_{\text{RBC}} = 3.2$ ns as opposed to $\tau_{\text{RBC-TB}} \sim 1.97$ ns, while the longer lifetime component remained relatively consistent within the margin of error ($\tau_{\text{RBC}} = 6.7$ ns vs. $\tau_{\text{RBC-TB}} \sim 6.2$ ns), as documented in Table 3.

Preincubation of RBCs with 5DAII, corresponding to RBC-5DAII, resulted in a lifetime of $\tau_{\text{RBC-5DAII}} = 7.66 \pm 0.09$ ns. As outlined in Table 3, fluorescence lifetime distribution values for RBCs preincubated with 5DAII and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB exhibited significantly higher amplitude values. These values suggested the presence

of three distinct components, each with different average lifetimes. Specifically, the average lifetime values for $\tau_{\text{RBC-5DAII-TB}}$ were 2.8...4.8 and 8.03 ns. However, looking to the single cell images only two components are present with the corresponding lifetimes $\tau_{\text{RBC-5DAII-TB}} = 2.8$ and 8.03 ns. Indicating that only those two components should be considered as fluorescence from RBC-5DAII.

Figure 21 illustrates the analysis of fractional intensity of fluorescence lifetime using phasor transformation of RBCs before and after incubation with 250 μM TB and 1 mg/mL 5DAII. The experiments were conducted with a λ_{ex} of 375 nm and a 460 nm long pass filter, with a 40 MHz laser repetition rate.

In detail:

- Panel (A) showcases the fluorescence lifetime distribution of control RBCs, revealing a distribution centered around two clusters at 7.82 ns and 3.04 ns.
- Panel (B) presents the phasor plot fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs incubated with TB, demonstrating an extended distribution within the range of 1.2 ns to 9.86 ns.
- Panel (C) displays the fluorescence lifetime distribution of cells treated solely with 5DAII, showing a central distribution around 11.3 ns.
- Panel (D) depicts the fluorescence lifetime distribution of RBCs preincubated with 5DAII and subsequently incubated with TB. This distribution is centered around 12.6 ns, with an extension towards shorter lifetimes.

These phasor plots allow for a graphical representation of the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes, offering insights into the changes in fluorescence characteristics of RBCs under different experimental conditions.

Calculations of properties of RBCs using a different approach were also performed using fit-free global phasor approach (Fig. 21). Phasor analysis enables isolating fluorescence lifetime parameters of separate components, where each cluster represents species with different luminescence properties [40-43]. TM (Modular fluorescence lifetime) values for the RBC main cluster were obtained at $TM_{RBC\ 1} = 7.82$ ns with a shorter lifetime of $TM_{RBC\ 2} = 3.04$ ns, while after incubation with 250 μ M TB (RBC-TB) $TM_{RBC-TB} = 1.20$ ns and $TM_{RBC-TB} = 9.86$ ns were observed. The cluster was located at $TM_{RBC-5DAII} = 11.29$ ns for RBC-5DAII, and for RBC-5DAII-TB the phasor fingerprint was centered at $TM_{RBC-5DAII-TB} = 12.69$ ns, with a trajectory towards shorter lifetimes.

An overlay of fractional fluorescence lifetime intensities of the samples after analysis of the first-harmonic (40 MHz) phasor plots in Figure 8 shows the virtual distribution of the fluorescence lifetimes in RBCs after treatment with 5DAII and/or TB as a virtual oxidation trajectory.

Figure 22 The analysis of fractional intensity of fluorescence lifetime using phasor transformation was performed on RBCs after treatment with 5DAII and TB. The experiments were conducted with a lex of 375 nm and a 460 nm long pass filter, with a 40 MHz laser repetition rate.

In the results:

- Control RBCs, as shown by the black eclipse in the phasor plot, display a fluorescence lifetime distribution concentrated within specific ranges.
- RBCs incubated with 250 μM TB, represented by another black eclipse, exhibit a wider fluorescence lifetime distribution indicative of oxidative stress conditions.
- RBCs incubated with 5DAII (1 mg/mL) only, as indicated within a black eclipse, show a distinct fluorescence lifetime distribution.
- RBCs preincubated with 5DAII (1 mg/mL) and subsequently incubated with 250 μM TB, denoted by the final black eclipse, present a unique fluorescence lifetime distribution.

The red line in the plot parallels the virtual oxidation trajectory of RBCs under TB-induced oxidative stress conditions. Additionally, a dashed line defines a hypothetical triangle that represents the expected lifetime distributions of RBCs under oxidative stress conditions and preincubated with 5DAII.

Interestingly, RBCs preincubated with 5DAII exhibit a lack of shorter fluorescence lifetimes within the oxidative stress range, suggesting a potential protective effect of 5DAII against oxidative stress-induced changes in fluorescence lifetimes.

The observed shift and distribution of fluorescence lifetimes and fractional intensities in RBCs could serve as a valuable graphical tool for investigating the oxidation and redox properties of RBCs in future studies. The emergence of new lifetime species on the RBC membrane, as depicted in Fig. 19D, indicates a potential interaction between 5DAII and the components of the RBC membrane. This suggests that 5DAII might have a meaningful interaction with the RBC membrane, further emphasizing its potential significance for studying oxidative stress and redox-related processes.

Photobiological properties of RBCs in OS preincubated with Alloxazine derivatives with extended aromaticity

Figure 23 Molecular structures of studied compounds - naphtho[2,3-g]pteridine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione (**1a**) and 1,3-dimethylnaphtho[2,3-g]pteridine-2,4(1H,3H)-dione (**1b**). Together with molecular structures of the alloxazines and isoalloxazines with marked diazadiene system "conformation" (based on [33]).

The photochemical properties of compounds 1a and 1b under oxidative stress conditions were investigated in vitro by conducting experiments involving human red blood cells (RBCs) and tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB). This analysis was carried out using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM), as depicted in Figure 24. The obtained data on the distribution of fluorescence lifetimes are presented in Table 4. This study aimed to provide insights into how compounds 1a and 1b interact with RBCs in the presence of oxidative stress induced by TB, and how these interactions are reflected in the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of the cells.

Figure 24 Fluorescence lifetime microscopy (FLIM) of RBCs was conducted with an excitation wavelength of 375 nm and an emission wavelength of 460 nm. The following incubation conditions were employed for the RBC samples:

- (A) RBCs incubated with 0.01 mg/ml of compound 1a.
- (B) RBCs incubated with 0.01 mg/ml of compound 1b.
- (C) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml of compound 1a and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB.
- (D) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml of compound 1b and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB.

In the resulting images, the color map represents the fluorescence lifetime, while the grayscale map represents the fluorescence intensity. The scale bars provided are each 30 μ m in length. These FLIM images were used to study the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of RBCs under different experimental conditions, shedding light on their potential responses to oxidative stress and treatment with the compounds 1a and 1b.

Table 4 The average distribution values of fluorescence lifetimes for red blood cells (RBCs) that were preincubated with either 1a or 1b (at a concentration of 0.01 mg/ml) and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB were determined using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM) at an excitation wavelength of 375 nm and an emission wavelength of 460 nm. The data were analyzed using single or, if required, double peak GaussAmp fits. The parameters obtained from the fits include the amplitude (A_i) represented as the number of photon counts per second (cps), the fluorescence lifetime maxima (τ) of the components, and the full width at half maximum (FWHM) of each fluorescence distribution. These values were derived from Figure 9s and represent the average of triplicate measurements with a sample size of more than 20.

RBC Treatment	τ_1 / ns	A_1 / Cps ($\times 10^3$)	FWHM ₁ / ns	τ_2 / ns	A_2 / Cps ($\times 10^3$)	FWHM ₂ / ns
Control (RBC)	3.2 $\pm$ 0.33	0.18	0.96	6.77 $\pm$ 0.53	0.37	2.57
RBC-TB-250 μ M	1.97 $\pm$ 0.38	1.32	0.63	6.22 $\pm$ 0.67	$\pm$ 0.57	2.38
1a	2.83 $\pm$ 0.09	0.75	2.81			
1b	2.36 $\pm$ 0.04	1.89	1.81			
1a-250 μM TB	1.81 $\pm$ 0.43	7.2	0.76			
1b-250 μM TB	2.06 $\pm$ 0.41	1.27	2.38			

The average fluorescence lifetime distribution values of red blood cells (RBCs) that were preincubated with 1a or 1b (at a concentration of 0.01 mg/ml) and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB were obtained through FLIM histogram analysis at an excitation wavelength of 375 nm and an emission wavelength of 460 nm. These data were further analyzed using single- or, if necessary, double-peak GaussAmp fits. The resulting lifetime and amplitude values were presented in Table 4.

For the control RBCs, the average lifetime values were measured to be approximately 3.2 $\pm$ 0.33 ns and 6.77 $\pm$ 0.53 ns. Some cells exhibited single exponential lifetimes, while others displayed double exponential values. Upon treating the RBCs with 250 μ M TB, noticeable changes were observed in the shorter lifetime, which decreased to around 1.97 $\pm$ 0.38 ns. However, longer lifetimes in the range of approximately 6.22 $\pm$ 0.67 ns were still evident in some cells within this spectral range.

In contrast, RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1a and subsequently treated with 250 μ M TB exhibited a shorter fluorescence lifetime of around $\approx$ 1.56 ns. When RBCs were solely treated with 1a, an average lifetime of approximately 2.9 ns was recorded.

Similarly, for RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1b and subsequently treated with 250 μ M TB, the average fluorescence lifetime did change without treatment with TB, shifting from 2.36 ns to 2.06 ns, respectively.

The average fluorescence lifetime histogram distribution for both RBCs preincubated with 1a or 1b exhibited single Gaussian fits, as depicted in Figure 8s. However, this approach did not facilitate manual separation of the shorter fluorescence lifetime component attributed to the influence of TB. Notably, there were changes observed in the amplitude of RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1b and subsequently exposed to 250 μ M TB, when compared to RBCs treated solely with TB. The findings suggest that the formation of the shorter lifetime component in the lifetime distribution is significantly reduced in RBCs that were pretreated with 1b prior to exposure to 250 μ M TB (1.3×10^3 compared to 7.2×10^3 cps for 1a). Additionally, a slightly greater shift in the autofluorescence lifetime of RBCs was observed in those pretreated with 1a (1.81 ± 0.43 ns) compared to 1b (2.06 ± 0.41 ns).

We also performed average fluorescence lifetime measurements in single RBCs without prior incubation with 1a, 1b, or TB (Fig. 9s), and compared these to control cells (3.2 ± 0.33 ns and 6.77 ± 0.53 ns), as well as to cells after incubation with 250 μ M TB (1.97 ± 0.38 ns). Interestingly, the results obtained were consistent with the FLIM results in RBC cell populations in terms of fluorescence lifetime. However, the amplitudes for each component sometimes exhibited variations in single cell measurements. Examining the fluorescence lifetime of individual RBCs pretreated with 1b before exposure to TB (2.12 ± 0.28 ns) reaffirmed previous findings, suggesting that the formation of the shorter component is notably reduced both quantitatively (amplitudes of 1.36×10^3 compared to 16×10^3 cps for 1a) and qualitatively (1.27 ± 0.21 ns) in terms of fluorescence lifetime. After pretreatment of RBCs with only 1a, the measured lifetime was 3.22 ± 0.14 ns, compared to 1b (2.35 ± 0.05 ns) (Fig. 9s). However, demixing the FLIM histogram to obtain information about cellular components was challenging, as the fluorescence of alloxazine derivatives overlapped with the autofluorescence of the cells in this method. The fluorescence lifetime data parameters were also determined through phasor plot analysis (Fig. 6). Phasor analysis allows us to extract fluorescence lifetime parameters from various components in a complex in vitro environment, where each cluster corresponds to species with distinct photochemical properties. In this study, a pulsed laser source

operating at a frequency of 40 MHz was utilized, and the data were processed using SimFCS 2 software from Globals Software at the University of California, Irvine, following the vendor's instructions. The analysis involves detecting pixel value clusters in specific regions of the phasor plot. In brief, the Phase of emitted light lags behind that of excitation by 45° . For single exponential decays, TP (phase lifetime) equals TM (modular lifetime), whereas for multiexponential decays, TP is less than TM and depends on the modulation frequency (ω). Mod represents the relative modulation factor, which is determined by applying sine and cosine transforms to the measured decay data, where the modulation frequency ω is obtained by multiplying the laser repetition rate (40 MHz) by 2π . The parameters "g" and "s" represent the values at the two coordinates (G, S) of the phasor plot.

The calculated values for TM, TP, Mod, and Phase are as follows:

- After incubation with 1a, the phasor cluster was located at Phase=19.8, Mod=0.606, TP=1.43 ns, and TM=3.211 ns.
- After incubation with 1b, the data exhibited a first harmonic phasor cluster (measured at 40 MHz) at Phase=16.8, Mod=0.657, TP=1.205 ns, and TM=2.87 ns.
- The expected phasor fingerprint for RBCs preincubated with 1a and then treated with 250 μ M TB, a free-radical producer, was centered at Phase=15.3, Mod=0.666, TP=1.092 ns, and TM=2.819 ns. Additionally, a new extension appeared alongside the semicircle at Phase=9.3, Mod=0.845, TP=0.654 ns, and TM=1.70 ns.
- For RBCs preincubated with 1b, the phasor data displayed Phase=15.4, Mod=0.621, TP=1.098 ns, and TM=3.109 ns (for $n>20$), with a dimmer extension compared to the 1a data.

These results reflect a single exponential fluorescence lifetime fingerprint for RBCs preincubated with 1a and 1b, with the presence of a shorter lifetime component specifically for 1a.

Figure 25. The first harmonic phasor transformation at 40 MHz and fractional intensity analysis were performed on the following samples:

- (A) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1a
- (B) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1b
- (C) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1a and subsequently treated with 250 μM TB
- (D) RBCs preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml 1b and subsequently treated with 250 μM TB

In each panel, the top section on the left side shows the average fluorescence intensity image of the RBCs, while the right side displays the first harmonic phasor transformation of the FLIM data at 40 MHz.

The analysis of fractional fluorescence lifetime intensity of single RBCs has provided insightful findings. It confirmed the emergence of a new short lifetime cluster for cells

preincubated with 1b (Phase=25.3, Mod=0.810, TP=1.877 ns, and TM=1.92 ns) and revealed a less dense area for cells treated with 1a (Phase=23.6, Mod=0.748, TP=1.738 ns, and TM=2.31 ns) (Fig. 7). These observations indicate that 1b possesses higher potential antioxidant properties compared to 1a, as it prevented the formation of a shorter fluorescence lifetime component in RBCs under oxidative stress conditions.

In general, the numerical values for TM obtained from phasor analysis for control cells and cells treated only with TB showed close proximity to those from lifetime distribution analysis. However, the phasor analysis revealed additional hidden parameters beyond the histogram. For RBCs treated solely with 1a (TM=3.211 ns) compared to $t \approx 2.83$ ns from lifetime distribution analysis, and 1b (TM=2.87 ns) compared to $t \approx 2.36$ ns. The samples pretreated with 1a and subsequently incubated with 250 μ M TB exhibited TM1=2.81 ns and TM2=1.70 ns compared to $t_1 \approx 1.81$ ns. Similarly, RBCs preincubated with 1b and then treated with 250 μ M TB had a TM=3.10 ns compared to $t \approx 2.06$ ns. Control samples displayed varying characteristics, with single TM=6.959 ns to double exponential TM1=3.40 ns and TM2=15.5 ns, compared to $t_1 \approx 3.2$ ns and $t_2 \approx 6.2$ ns. In the context of OS and response to treatment, further investigation is warranted to elucidate the source of differences in lifetime distribution within the FLIM histogram of RBC control cells, but this topic is beyond the scope of this article.

Figure 26 . First harmonic phasor transformation and fractional intensity analysis (40MHz) of FLIM images of single RBC (A) preincubated with 0.01 mg/ml **1a** and then

with 250 μM TB, (B) preincubated with 0.01 mg/mL **1b** and then incubated with 250 μM TB.

Double spectral analysis of RBC intrinsic fluorescence lifetime in oxidative stress conditions

To study fluorescence lifetime images acquired by FLIM, phasor analysis conversion was applied. Phasor analysis converts FLIM data by Fourier transformation to the polar plots in which phasor points originating from different pixels in the image are represented by their location in the phasor plot (in Cartesian coordinates, we use the g and s coordinates that are the projections of the polar coordinates in the coordinate axes)[107]. Selecting the region of interest in the phasor plot represent the calculated parameters of the parts of the image from which those phasor points originate, the distribution of the photons with different lifetime decay produces an extended area of uncertainty. Analysis of the FLIM data in the phasor space was performed by detecting clusters of pixel values in specific regions of the phasor plot. Briefly, the phase of the emitted light lags beyond that of excitation by 45° . In the case of single-exponential decays $TP = TM$, while for multi-exponential decays $TP < TM$ and depends on the modulation frequency ω [127]. Mod represents the modulation factor, which is derived by applying the sine and cosine transforms to the measured decay data where the modulation frequency ω is derived from the laser repetition angular frequency and is calculated by multiplying the laser repetition rate (40 MHz) by 2π , and g and s represent the values at the two coordinates (G , S) of the phasor plot (detailed descriptions are available elsewhere[107]). The calculated values of TM (modular lifetime), TP (phase lifetime), Mod (relative modulation), and Phase are listed below. Fluorescence lifetime distribution analysis in RBCs in the different oxidative stress conditions have been studied using different $\lambda_{\text{ex}}/\lambda_{\text{em}}$ protocols (using $\lambda_{\text{ex}}=375\text{nm}$ and 640 nm and $\lambda_{\text{em}}= 460\text{ nm}$ and 690 nm). To induce oxidative stress we used TBHP (tert-butyl hydroperoxide or TB) in different concentrations (100, 250 μM) and a standard antioxidant Trolox (Tx) in different concentrations (0.01, 01, 1 mg/ml) to observe spectral and temporal changes of autofluorescence lifetime of RBCs

Figure 27: RBCs were subjected to incubation with different concentrations of Tx, yielding the following scenarios: (A) Control cells without Tx, (B) 0.01 mg/ml Tx, (C) 0.1 mg/ml Tx, and (D) 1 mg/ml Tx. Phasor transformation of FLIM images was performed on RBCs both in their normal state and after treatment with Tx ($\lambda_{ex}=375$ nm / $\lambda_{em}=460$ nm using a 40 MHz laser repetition rate). The phasor plot serves as a primary representation of control and Tx-treated cells, providing a global fingerprint of RBCs under these respective conditions. For control cells (A), the phasor plot exhibited Phase= 21.3, Mod= 0.512, TP= 1.554 ns, and TM= 3.884 ns, with data collected from more than 20 RBCs. Upon incubation with 0.01 mg/ml Tx (B), the anticipated phasor fingerprint was centered at Phase= 21.8, Mod= 0.300, TP= 1.591 ns, and TM= 6.08 ns (C). Subsequently, after incubation with 1 gm/ml Tx (D), the main cluster was observed at Phase= 17.8, Mod= 0.659, TP= 1.275 ns, and TM= 2.862, also based on data from more than 20 RBCs. Importantly, no smoothing filter was applied during the data processing.

In Figure 26, first harmonic fluorescence lifetime of RBCs without prior OS treatment (without TB) have been incubated with different concentration of Tx. Visual and temporal changes compared and the result confirmed that Tx may infer non oxidative changes to the TP and TM of the longer fluorescence lifetime fraction of control RBCs in the non-OS range (>2.0 ns).

Figure 26 illustrates the first harmonic fluorescence lifetime changes in RBCs that were not previously exposed to oxidative stress (TB) but were incubated with various concentrations of Tx. Through visual and temporal comparisons, it was established that Tx administration could induce non-oxidative changes in the TP and TM of the longer fluorescence lifetime portion of control RBCs in the non-oxidative stress (non-OS) range (above 2.0 ns).

In the context of RBCs treated with TB (as depicted in Fig. 27B-C), distinct alterations in the phasor global fingerprint of RBC lifetime fractions were observed in comparison to control cells (Fig. 27A). Earlier, we identified two lifetime fractions for RBCs treated with TB, which delineates two distinct ranges: 1) the normal range and 2) the oxidative stress (OS) range (Fig. 27A). With the application of higher concentrations of TB, the fraction transitions towards the shorter side (OS range), accompanied by an increase in fluorescence intensity.

Figure 28 : Incubation of RBCs with TB only (A)Control cells without TB (B)After incubation with 100 μ M TB (C) After incubation with 250 μ M TB (1.5 H, 37 $^{\circ}$ C) Phasor transformation of FLIM images of RBCs in both normal cells and after incubation with

100 and 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=375$ nm/ $\lambda_{\text{em}}=460$ nm at 40 MHz laser repetition. (A) Control cells present two populations at Phase= 19.9 Mod= 0.474 TP= 1.443 ns TM= 4.187 ns and second at Phase= 17.0 Mod= 0.649 TP= 1.213 ns TM= 2.927 from $n>20$ RBCs (B) after incubation with 100 μM Phase= 11.3 Mod= 0.851 TP= 0.796 ns TM= 1.667 ns from $n>20$ RBCs. (C) Expected phasor fingerprint after incubation with 250 μM TB mg/ml was centered at Phase= 8.2 Mod= 0.840 TP= 0.571 ns TM= 1.738 ns. No smoothing filter has been applied to process the data.

Figure 29 illustrates the phasor transformation of FLIM images of RBCs pre/post incubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and various concentrations of TB (100 μM , 250 μM) using a laser repetition rate of 40 MHz. Upon an overall comparison of the effect of Tx, it becomes evident that Tx seems to exhibit more pronounced effectiveness at a lower concentration of TB (100 μM). This effect is observed whether Tx is applied to the cells prior to or after incubation with TB, as shown in Figure 29-A and Figure 29-B, in contrast to Figure 29-C and Figure 29-D. In these cases, the cluster's behavior shifts towards resembling the characteristics of neutral cells, as depicted in Figure 28A.

Figure 29 : In Figure 29, the phasor transformation of FLIM images of RBCs is depicted before and after incubation with 0.1 mg/ml Tx, alongside various concentrations of TB (100 μ M, 250 μ M), using a laser repetition rate of 40 MHz and λ_{ex} =375 nm / λ_{em} = 460 nm. The different scenarios are illustrated as follows: (A) RBCs preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then incubated with 100 μ M TB: The resulting cluster is situated at Phase= 15.1, Mod= 0.664, TP= 1.076 ns, and TM= 2.828 ns. The distribution is narrow and extends towards the longer range. (B) RBCs pretreated with 100 μ M TB and then 0.1 mg/ml Tx: The cluster is observed at Phase= 17.6, Mod= 0.653, TP= 1.262 ns, and TM= 2.898 ns. (C) RBCs preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then incubated with 250 μ M TB: The resulting cluster is centered at Phase= 16.6, Mod= 0.791, TP= 1.185 ns, and TM= 2.044 ns. (D) RBCs pretreated with 250 μ M TB and then incubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx: The cluster appears at Phase= 11.0, Mod= 0.864, TP= 0.775 ns, and TM= 1.576 ns. These results showcase the distinctive effects of Tx and TB on RBCs when it comes to their phasor transformation characteristics.

In the separate experiment shown in Figure 30, the effects of pre/post incubation with Tx were investigated using a higher concentration of TB (250 μ M) and different concentrations of Tx (0.01, 0.1, 1 mg/ml) with reverse protocols. The results indicated distinct differences between the visual plots of cells treated with higher Tx concentrations (0.1, 1 mg/ml) compared to lower concentrations (0.01, 0.1 mg/ml) after incubation with 250 μ M TB.

- Prior incubation with higher concentrations of Tx (0.1, 1 mg/ml) resulted in a longer fluorescence lifetime fraction of RBCs after incubation with 250 μ M TB (Fig. 30 C and E).

- Post incubation with lower concentrations of Tx (0.01, 0.1 mg/ml) shifted the overall single fraction of oxidized RBCs towards the range of normal cells (Fig. 30 D and F).

These findings suggest that the use of different concentrations of Tx in pre/post incubation can have varying effects on the fluorescence lifetime of RBCs after exposure to oxidative stress induced by TB.

Figure 30 : presents the results of RBC incubation with Tx and TB using reverse protocols. The experimental conditions and the resulting clusters are described as follows:

- Control cells (A): Single cluster with characteristics Phase= 17.08, Mod= 0.659, TP= 1.275 ns, TM= 2.862 ns.
- Incubation with 250 μ M TB (B): Two clusters, one centered at Phase= 11.7, Mod= 0.792, TP= 0.826 ns, TM= 2.037 ns, and another cluster at Phase= 14.7, Mod= 0.564, TP= 1.043 ns, TM= 3.496 ns.
- Preincubation with 1 mg/ml Tx and then 250 μ M TB (C): Two distinct clusters, one at Phase= 11.7, Mod= 0.792, TP= 0.826 ns, TM= 2.037 ns, and another at Phase= 18.4, Mod= 0.442, TP= 1.321 ns, TM= 4.470 ns.
- Preincubation with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then 250 μ M TB (D): Two clusters at Phase= 12.4, Mod= 0.786, TP= 0.875 ns, TM= 2.074 ns, and Phase= 18.3, Mod= 0.530, TP= 1.316 ns, TM= 3.748 ns.
- Preincubation with 0.01 mg/ml Tx and then 250 μ M TB (E): Phase= 14.8, Mod= 0.738, TP= 1.050 ns, TM= 2.372 ns, similar to the result in Figure 30B.
- Post incubation with 1 mg/ml Tx after treatment with 250 μ M TB (F): Phase= 13.4, Mod= 0.793, TP= 0.948 ns, TM= 2.035 ns, resembling Figure 4B and 4G as an oxidized form.
- Post incubation with 0.1 mg/ml Tx after treatment with 250 μ M TB (G): Phase= 15.8, Mod= 0.702, TP= 1.129 ns, TM= 2.594 ns, slightly less than control cells (Figure 30A).
- Post incubation with 0.01 mg/ml Tx after treatment with 250 μ M TB (H): Phase= 15.5, Mod= 0.813, TP= 1.106 ns, TM= 3.185 ns, which falls within the control RBC zone with a narrow extension towards the oxidized form.

Comparison between the different plots suggests that Tx pre and post incubation may be more effective at lower concentrations of TB (100 μ M). In higher concentrations of TB (250 μ M), the pretreatment with TB might alter the distribution of changes observed.

The comparison between the fluorescence lifetime fractions of cells that were either pre- or post-incubated with Tx reveals that TB incubation with 100 μ M (Fig. 5A) results in a smaller fraction of short-lived fluorescence lifetimes compared to the cells incubated with a higher concentration of TB (250 μ M). This suggests that lower concentrations of TB induce less oxidation of the RBC membrane and its main constituent, hemoglobin (Hb). When comparing Figure 31A and 31B, it becomes evident that the oxidative stress (OS) status of the RBCs and the distribution of the

shorter fluorescence lifetime component are dependent on the concentrations of both TB and Tx. This indicates that the interplay between the oxidative stress inducer (TB) and the protective agent (Tx) is complex and can influence the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of RBCs.

Figure 31 presents a three-dimensional fluorescence lifetime distribution plot of RBCs after pre/post incubation with 0.1 mg/ml Tx, along with two different concentrations of TB: (A) 100 μM TB and (B) 250 μM TB. This plot provides a comprehensive visualization of how the distribution of fluorescence lifetime components changes in response to different combinations of Tx and TB concentrations. The distinct shapes and positions of the clusters in the plot reveal the oxidative stress status of the RBCs and highlight the dependence of the distribution of the shorter fluorescence lifetime component on the specific concentrations of TB and Tx used. This further emphasizes the complex relationship between oxidative stress, the protective effects of Tx, and the resulting fluorescence lifetime characteristics observed in RBCs.

The analysis of Hb-depleted cells (ghost cells) provides valuable insights into the underlying mechanism of both tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB) and the compound being investigated (Tx) in the context of oxidative stress (OS). In the context of fluorescence lifetime, the following observations are made:

1. Complete Cells with Hb in Oxidized State: The fluorescence lifetime analysis of complete cells (including both membrane and cellular content) that are subjected to oxidative stress (OS) and treated with either TB or Tx reveals the presence of double clusters in the fluorescence lifetime distribution. These clusters are located at around ~ 1.9 ns and ~ 5.5 ns. This suggests that there are two distinct fluorescence lifetime fractions present in the complete cells under oxidized conditions.

2. Ghost Cells (Membrane Only) in Oxidized State: When analyzing Hb-depleted ghost cells, which only consist of the cell membrane without the presence of hemoglobin, their fluorescence lifetime distribution is primarily centered around ~ 5.5 ns. This indicates that the longer fluorescence lifetime fraction is attributed to the cell membrane in an oxidized state.

By comparing the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of complete cells and ghost cells, it becomes evident that the shorter fluorescence lifetime fraction (~ 1.9 ns) in complete cells corresponds to the cellular content, whereas the longer fluorescence lifetime fraction (~ 5.5 ns) is associated with the cell membrane in an oxidized state. This insight provides a better understanding of the distribution changes observed in the fluorescence lifetime data of RBCs under oxidative stress conditions and their response to treatments with TB and Tx.

Figure 32 depicts a line plot histogram aimed at determining the contribution of hemoglobin (Hb) to the overall fluorescence lifetime of RBCs. The comparison is made between two scenarios: (A) RBCs in an oxidative stress (OS) state without any specific treatments. (B) Hb-depleted ghost RBCs that lack hemoglobin. These measurements are performed using a laser excitation wavelength of 375 nm and an emission wavelength of 460 nm, with a 40 MHz laser repetition rate. By comparing the fluorescence lifetime characteristics of these two scenarios, it becomes possible to assess the influence of hemoglobin on the overall fluorescence lifetime of RBCs and its potential role in the observed lifetime distribution changes under oxidative stress conditions.

The data presented in Figures 32 and 33 provide valuable insights into the impact of Tx on the membrane and hemoglobin (Hb) components of red blood cells (RBCs) under different experimental conditions. The phasor transformation of FLIM images at different excitation/emission wavelengths was performed to discern the effects of Tx on these cellular components.

Specifically, in Figure 32, RBCs that were preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then treated with 250 μ M TB (λ_{ex} =375 nm/ λ_{em} =460 nm) displayed a longer fluorescence lifetime associated with the RBC membrane. This observation suggests that Tx may have a protective effect on the RBC membrane, potentially inhibiting oxidation or preserving its integrity under oxidative stress conditions induced by TB.

Furthermore, Figure 33 highlights the differential response of RBCs to Tx treatment at different excitation/emission wavelengths. The phasor transformation results suggest that the effects of Tx are more pronounced at shorter wavelengths (λ_{ex} =375 nm/ λ_{em} =460 nm), which correspond to the RBC membrane. In contrast, the impact of Tx is not as evident at longer wavelengths (λ_{ex} =640 nm/ λ_{em} =690 nm), which correspond to the Porphyrins, including hemoglobin (Hb).

Taken together, these findings indicate that Tx may play a role in preserving the RBC membrane from oxidative damage, with a potentially lesser impact on the Porphyrin components, such as Hb. This information contributes to a deeper understanding of the molecular interactions and protective mechanisms of Tx within RBCs under conditions of oxidative stress.

Figure 33 Figure 33 depicts the first harmonic transformation of FLIM (Fluorescence Lifetime Imaging Microscopy) images of red blood cells (RBCs) at different excitation/emission wavelengths. The specific conditions for each panel are described below:

- A) RBCs after Incubation with 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=640$ nm/ $\lambda_{\text{em}}=690$ nm)
- B) RBCs after Incubation with 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=640$ nm/ $\lambda_{\text{em}}=690$ nm)
- C) RBCs Preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then with 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=375$ nm/ $\lambda_{\text{em}}=460$ nm)
- D) RBCs Preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml Tx and then with 250 μM TB ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=375$ nm/ $\lambda_{\text{em}}=460$ nm)

The primary purpose of this analysis is to explore changes in the phasor plot fingerprint of RBCs under different experimental conditions. The figures highlight how pretreatment with 0.1 mg/ml Tx at shorter excitation wavelengths ($\lambda_{\text{ex}}=375$ nm) corresponding to the RBC membrane results in changes in the phasor plot fingerprint. However, these changes are not observed at longer excitation

wavelengths ($\lambda_{ex}=640$ nm) corresponding to the Q-band region of Porphyrins, which includes hemoglobin (Hb).

This observation suggests that the effects of pretreatment with 0.1 mg/ml Tx primarily influence the RBC membrane rather than the Porphyrins (Hb). The differences in phasor plot fingerprints at different excitation wavelengths provide insights into the specific interactions and changes occurring within the RBCs under the influence of Tx and TB treatments.

In Figure 34, the investigation into the presence of TB-induced peroxy radicals and the potential antioxidant effects of 5DAII is depicted. The setup involves the interaction between various components, as explained below:

- Panel B: RBCs Incubated with 250 μ M TB - This panel shows the fluorescence lifetime response of RBCs after being treated with 250 μ M TB. The oxidative stress induced by TB treatment can lead to the formation of peroxy radicals.

- Panel C: RBCs Preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml 5DAII and then 250 μ M TB - This panel demonstrates the fluorescence lifetime response of RBCs that were first preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml of 5DAII and then exposed to 250 μ M TB. The presence of 5DAII suggests potential antioxidant effects, and its interaction with TB-induced oxidative stress is examined.

- Panel D: RBCs Preincubated with 250 μ M TB and then 0.1 mg/ml 5DAII - This panel shows the fluorescence lifetime response of RBCs that were initially treated with 250 μ M TB and subsequently preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml of 5DAII. This arrangement studies the interaction between the oxidative stress from TB and the potential antioxidant effect of 5DAII.

In Panel D (Fig. 34D), the presence of lipid peroxy radicals is indicated before the introduction of 5DAII. The interaction between lipid peroxy radicals and 5DAII is suggested to produce TBARS (thiobarbituric acid reactive substances) granules with longer fluorescence lifetime values compared to situations involving only 5DAII (Fig. 34C) or only TB (Fig. 34B).

The use of reduced laser power (1/8) in panel D (Fig. 34D) enabled the imaging of long lifetime fractions, which are likely associated with the presence of these granules.

Fluorescence lifetime values obtained from these experiments are further analyzed and presented in Table 3, The values presented in the table are average fluorescence lifetime values (τ) for different RBC samples under various conditions as analyzed using FLIM with a laser excitation wavelength of 375 nm and emission wavelength of 460 nm. The values are provided with their standard deviations ($\pm$) and have been obtained through least square fits analysis with a χ^2 value approximately equal to 1.0. The "Amplitude" column represents the amplitude of the fluorescence lifetime component, and the "Lifetime" column represents the fluorescence lifetime maxima (τ) of the respective components. with the least squares fits ($\chi^2 \approx 1.0$) method used for the analysis. These values provide insights into the different interactions and conditions explored in the study.

Figure 34 Figure 34 illustrates the fluorescence lifetime responses of red blood cells (RBCs) under different experimental conditions:

A. Control Cells with PBS Buffer: This panel represents the baseline fluorescence lifetime of RBCs in the absence of any treatment, serving as a control reference.

B. RBCs Incubated with 250 μM TB: In this panel, RBCs were subjected to treatment with 250 μM TB for 30 minutes at 37.5°C. The resulting fluorescence lifetime distribution reflects the changes induced by the oxidative stress caused by TB treatment.

C. RBCs Preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml 5DAII and then 250 μM TB: Here, RBCs were preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml of 5DAII before being exposed to 250 μM TB. The fluorescence lifetime response observed in this panel represents the interaction between the lipid peroxy radical (5DAII) and the oxidative stress induced by TB treatment.

D. RBCs Preincubated with 250 μM TB and then 0.1 mg/ml 5DAII: In this panel, RBCs were first treated with 250 μM TB and then preincubated with 0.1 mg/ml of 5DAII. The fluorescence lifetime distribution here indicates the influence of the sequential treatment with TB followed by 5DAII on the RBCs.

The key takeaway from this figure is that the fluorescence lifetime responses provide insights into the interactions between TB, 5DAI1, and the oxidative stress conditions within RBCs. The differences in fluorescence lifetimes between the panels demonstrate the complex interplay of these factors and their impact on the cellular components. In particular, the longer lifetime observed in panel D suggests an interaction between lipid peroxy radicals and 5DAI1, potentially influencing the oxidative state of the RBCs.

Classical MD analysis

First, we have used the CHARMM-GUI web interface [128] to build a solvated bilayer containing 94 lipids and 6035 water molecules with a hydration rate of 55 water molecules per lipid. The lipid area of 4689 in both upper and lower leaflets. We have equilibrated pure lipid bilayer in water containing 0.137 mM NaCl and 0.02 mM KCl (Table 1S) corresponding to experimental PBS buffer which have been used in experimental analysis. This system underwent 5 cycles of equilibration between 5-100 ps in 310.5 K. The resulting tetragonal box size after equilibration was $\sim 68.5 \times 68.5 \times 85 \text{ \AA}^3$. Computed energy is reported in table 2. Figure 35 represents a side view snapshot of the heterogeneous lipid bilayer in hydration box

Figure 35 showcases a snapshot of a synthetic heterogeneous lipid bilayer within a hydration box. This bilayer is composed of 45% cholesterol (RCSB: CHL1) and 55 mol% phospholipids. The phospholipids consist of approximately 29% phosphatidylcholines (RCSB: DPPC), 27% phosphatidylethanolamines (RCSB: DMPE), 25% sphingomyelins (RCSB: DSM), and 15% phosphatidylserines (RCSB: CER6), all generated using the CHARMM-GUI platform. The snapshot visualizations were created using Schrödinger Maestro 13.1 software.

Figure 36 Model of hydrophobic interactions between 5-Deazaalloxazine and synthetic heterogenous lipid membrane.

Figure 37 Model of hydrophobic interactions between lumichrom and heterogenous synthetic lipid membrane.

To explore the interaction with oxidized cholesterol surfaces, a set of 10 oxidized cholesterol residues (5,6-epoxycholesterol) was introduced into the hydration box along with the synthetic membrane. Through the use of Schrödinger Maestro 13.1 software, these oxidized cholesterol residues were aligned with the synthetic membrane constituents, enabling a thorough study of ligand interactions. Subsequent analysis revealed no direct interactions between lumichrome, 5DAII, and the 5,6-epoxycholesterol residues (Figure 36). This finding was further substantiated by employing the CHARMM-GUI web interface, which leveraged available free energy perturbation (FEP) and thermodynamic integration (TI) modules.

Phosphatidylethanolamines (PEs) are prominently present in cellular membranes and lipoproteins. The oxidation of PEs' fatty acyl chains leads to the generation of various oxidized products, each exerting a multitude of biological functions that have not yet been fully unraveled. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) play a role in modifying the unsaturated fatty acyl chains of PE through mechanisms involving oxygen insertions and chain-decomposition reactions.[129,130] [131,132].

Figure 38 illustrates the proposed model depicting the interaction between 5,6-epoxycholesterol, a byproduct of tert-butyl hydroperoxide (TB)-induced cholesterol peroxidation, and alloxazine derivatives. Despite our investigations, direct interactions between the ligands and oxidized cholesterol species were not observed. The

simulation was conducted with water represented by the TIP3 model. This model helps visualize the potential relationship between the components and sheds light on the complex interplay within the system.

Discussion

Discussion

Upon oxidative stress by TB a number of different spectrochemical processes may occur in RBCs namely in human erythrocytes: (1) reduced glutathione oxidation; (2) oxyHb oxidation; (3) metHb accumulation; (4) ferryl form of Hb accumulation; (5) peroxidation of membrane lipids (formation of lipofuscin and ceroid pigments); (6) chemiluminescence [84] with different spectral and temporal properties. Due to contribution of different cell component to the overall photochemical properties of RBC we obtained fluorescence decay of Hb in the range ($\lambda_{ex} = 640 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{em} = 690 \text{ nm}$) using fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM). Changes to the absorption spectra of RBC at 630-640 nm which is observed as an increase in the arbitrary units (Fig. 1 B-D blue line) [104] may contribute to formation of highly oxidized Hb in (Fig 5B) with a lifetime of $\tau = 1.54 \text{ ns}$ corresponding to Hb according to Saytashev et al. [86]. By adding 0.1 mg/ml Tx the lifetime distribution of the cells in the OS will be reduced (Fig. 6D-F compared to Fig. 6A-C) but the overall fluorescence lifetime decay contributing to subforms of Hb will not change visually. We may define a Redox plot in Fig. 7B (red eclipse) which is present in highly oxidized cells but not normal cells in Fig. 7A. Although most autofluorescence may be correlated with production of lipid peroxy radicals [88,118,119] after incubation with TB, we have tried to reduce lipofuscin contribution by adding the Tx [123,126] as a standard antioxidant and to select the proper wavelength [87]. FLIM studies of RBCs provides possibility of a label-free, fit-free, and sensitive method to identify different metabolic states of RBCs in different redox conditions to evaluate small changes in the redox states of cells and predict cell conditions. The FLIM is a promising non-invasive optical tool for monitoring metabolic changes during oxidative stress or disease progression in unlabeled tissues. $\tau\phi$ histogram of the FLIM image is represented in black histogram correspond to $\tau\phi$ of each image component identified by the number of photons detected in counting time intervals. Phasor transformation enables us to observe a fingerprint of RBC fluorescence lifetime without complications of fitting and distribution analysis. This method is sensitive enough to study intrinsic fluorescence lifetime of RBCs which mostly corresponds to PP IX porphyrin heme group and partially to the outer cell membrane. Using the longer wavelength ($\lambda_{ex} 640 \text{ nm} - \lambda_{ex} 690 \text{ nm}$) for excitation and detection however reduces the possibility of noise level in the study of oxidative. We could observe that prior incubation of RBCs with Tx may shift the fluorescence lifetime

of the RBCs toward the longer fluorescence lifetime. This shift could be observed by analyzing the fluorescence lifetime histogram of RBCs but not the phasor plots. Prior incubation of RBCs with standard Tx present RBCs capacity to employ exogenous antioxidants

Upon oxidative stress by TB a number of different spectrochemical processes may occur in RBCs namely in human erythrocytes: (1) reduced glutathione oxidation; (2) oxyHb oxidation; (3) metHb accumulation; (4) ferryl form of Hb accumulation; (5) peroxidation of membrane lipids (formation of lipofuscin and ceroid pigments); (6) chemiluminescence [84]. We could observe a longer and shorter living fluorescence lifetime corresponding to Intrinsic tryptophan fluorescence of human Hb[89] or products of lipid peroxidation with fluorescence lifetime ranging from picoseconds to around ~8.30 ns[88,118,119] and porphyrin IX rings (lifetime ?) . Analysing longer component by RBC ghost cells correlates the fluorescent to the membrane and presumably product of membrane lipid peroxidation (lipofuscin and ceroid pigments) usually named age pigments which are accompanied by the appearance of high molecular weight proteins or polymeric lipid-protein complexes Having a strong fluorescence with a maximum in the region of 430–490 nm on excitation which have been characterized by several investigators with ultraviolet light. The pigments are probably composed of heterogeneous complexes including lipid-soluble and lipid-insoluble fluorescent lipid peroxidation products[118,119] Fluorescence lifetime of extracted lipofuscin granules in chloroform are reported as 3 exponential 0.2 ns, 1.8 ns , 6.3 ns using similar setup [88]. Removing the Hb from ghost cells most of the shorter lifetime component disappeared in RBCs. The other shorter fraction of fluorescent lifetime may correspond to the Porphyrin rings in methemoglobin ~ 3.9 ns[133]

Intrinsic fluorescence lifetime of RBCs and Hb in $\lambda_{ex}= 640 \text{ nm}$ / $\lambda_{em}= 690 \text{ nm}$ could not be directly measured by fluorescence lifetime spectroscopy because the number of emitted photons was too low and therefore photochemical properties have not been reported by a spectrofluorometer in this study. In our study addition of Tx enabled stable and prolonged intrinsic fluorescence of the cell.[123,124] after peroxidation with

higher concentrations of TB. While an understanding of the working principle of Tx is yet missing, a combination of an oxidizing and reducing system ROXS (reduction and oxidation system) has similarly proven its applicability in single-molecule as well as super resolution applications.[125,126]. This combination of oxidizing and reducing reactions may explain adverse effects of Tx concentration which has been observed in (Fig. 1B-D and Fig.4 D-H) where increasing Tx concentration from 0.01 mg/ml to 1mg/ml leaves the cell in OS conditions as suggested by corresponding graphical phasor plots.

FLIM of protoporphyrin IX lifetime has already been used in guided tumor visualization in neurosurgery [133]. Double spectral FLIM may be used to determine changes in the autofluorescence of the tissues and to determine metabolic and oxidative stress and furthermore as an auxiliary proof to study underlying mechanism of the changes in different cells.

Interaction between the synthetic lipid membrane and the alloxazine derivatives, lumichrome and 5Deaza alloxazine appeared to be rather based on hydrophobic membrane interactions. Preparation of highly detailed RBC membrane and consequent analysis will be interesting. Due to the nature of RBC alloxazine presence of mitochondrial and plasma membrane riboflavin transporters[134] has to be studied and reviewed further. Three riboflavin transporters (RFVT 1-3) has been identified [135–137] which could be target of competitive inhibitors and riboflavin analogs roseoflavin, lumiflavin and lumichrome, and co-factor derivatives FMN and FAD.[138]

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کانون پزشکی و حقوق ایران

کانون پزشکی و حقوق ایران، با عنایت به تکلیف‌های ناشی از امر برادر فارغ التحصیل
و فعالیت در عرصه‌های علمی با عنایت به دفاعیات

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شماره ثبت کتابخانه ملی

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آقمر خانم

امیرعلی داودپور

از پانزده نامه با عنوان فارسی

تجزیه و تحلیل ظرفیت آنتی اکسیدانی گلبول های قرمز خون در شرایط استرس اکسیداتیو
با استفاده از میکروسکوپ تصویربرداری طول عمر فلورسنت

پانزده نامه با عنوان انگلیسی

**Analysis of antioxidant capacity of red blood cells in
oxidative stress conditions utilizing fluorescent lifetime
imaging microscopy (FLIM)**

در رشته

بیوشیمی

در تاریخ

۱۴۰۲/۱۰/۹

در مقطع

دکترای تخصصی

با رجه

بسیار خوب

کوپان نامه فوق را برادر تریغ و پاسداشت فعالیت ایشان در پزشکی - برادر احمد اینمید که از مزایای آنس برخوردار شود

دکتر امیرعلی تهماسب
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دکتر بزرگمهر زندی
کانون پزشکی و حقوق ایران
مدیر کانون پزشکی و حقوق ایران

مهر و امضا کانون

KARTA PRZEBIEGU STUDIÓW
UNIWERSYTET IM. ADAMA MICKIEWICZA W POZNANIU

INFORMACJE O STUDENCIE

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INFORMACJE O OSIĄGNIĘCIACH

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<i>Rok akademicki 2018/2019</i>			
<i>(02-CCB2G) Career Core Box - do you [truly] THINK about ypur scientific career?</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-PZG) Praktyka zawodowa</i>	<i>cw 90</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>(02-PDFG) Przygotowanie do dydaktyki szczegółowej – chemia fizyczna i teoretyczna</i>	<i>sem 13</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SGBNG) Seminarium grupy badawczej</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SMTG) Small Molecule Tools in Modern Chemical Biology</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[3,5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-TAS2G) Talking about science to non scientific audiences</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-WPBNG) Wstęp do prowadzenia badań naukowych</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Semestr letni 2018/2019</i>			
<i>(03-KJP4-SL) Kurs języka polskiego (4 godziny tygodniowo)</i>	<i>lek 60</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Rok akademicki 2019/2020</i>			
<i>(02-ABC2G) ABC of Research Integrity in the European Research Area</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-DPEG) Design principles for nanoporous carbo-based materials in Energy Storage and Energy Conversion Applications</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[4,5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-HIR2G) How to manage international research project. Best way of being the good manager.</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-PZG) Praktyka zawodowa</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>(56-RUT) Rethinking university teaching.</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4,5]</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>(02-SGBG) Seminarium grupy badawczej</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[3]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SN2G) Sympozium naukowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Semestr zimowy 2019/2020</i>			
<i>(02-CRIA) Crystallography I: Elements</i>	<i>wyk 15 / lab 30</i>	<i>[3,5/3]</i>	<i>5</i>

Przedmioty wg cykli dydaktycznych	Zajęcia/godziny	Ocena	ECTS
<i>Rok akademicki 2020/2021</i>			
(02-HCG) Heterogeneous catalysis – a pillar of the green chemistry and sustainable development	wyk 12	[3]	1
(02-NATG) Nucleic acid-targeting molecular systems: from chemistry to biomedical applications	wyk 15	[5]	1
(02-PZG) Praktyka zawodowa	cw	[4]	4
(02-SGBG) Seminarium grupy badawczej	cw	[5]	1
(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe	wyk	[4]	1
<i>Rok akademicki 2021/2022</i>			
(02-ACW2G) Academic writing	war 15	[4]	1
(02-MOC2G) Mechanochemical organic and coordination chemistry	cw 18	[5]	1
(02-SADSG) Self-assembly of dynamic systems	wyk 10	[3]	1
(02-SGBG) Seminarium grupy badawczej	cw	[3]	1
(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe	wyk	[3]	1
(02-SSPA2G) Soft skills - the practical approach	war 30	[5]	2
(02-STA2G) Statistics	war 15	[4]	1
(02-SN2G) Sympozjum naukowe	wyk	[4]	1
(02-OCBVG) The Organic Chemistry of the B Vitamins	wyk 10	[3]	
Razem ECTS:			52

KIEROWNIK

 prof. UAM dr hab. Piotr Pawluć

UNIwersYTET IM. ADAMA MICKIEWICZA W POZNANIU
 Wydział Chemii
 Biuro Obsługi Studentów
 ul. Uniwersytetu Poznańskiego 8, 61-614 Poznań
 tel. +48 61 829 15 64, +48 61 829 16 01,
 +48 61 829 16 04

Podpis i pieczęć kierownika studiów doktoranckich

Pieczęć urzędowa uczelni

Uczelnia stosuje następujący system ocen

bdb	5
db+	4,5
db	4
dst+	3,5
dst	3
ndst	2
zaliczone	zal
nie zaliczone	nzal

Opis kodów typów zajęć

cw	ćwiczenia
lab	zajęcia laboratoryjne
lek	lektorat z języka obcego
sem	seminarium
war	warsztat
wyk	wykład

Oceny bez nawiasu są ocenami z przedmiotu, oceny w nawiasie są ocenami z zajęć, pionowa kreska oddziela oceny z różnych zajęć, średnik oddziela oceny z różnych protokołów, spacja oddziela oceny na tym samym protokole, kolejność ocen w ramach protokołu odpowiada kolejności terminów. ZAL = zaliczony bez oceny, NZAL = niezaliczony, — = brak ocen na protokole.

TRANSCRIPT OF RECORDS
ADAM MICKIEWICZ UNIVERSITY, POZNAŃ

INFORMATION ON THE STUDENT

Surname: *Davoudpour*
First name(s): *Amirali*
Date of birth (day, month, year): *16.09.1979*
Student identification number or code: *153098*

INFORMATION ON THE STUDIES

Name of the programme: *Studia doktoranckie na Wydziale Chemii HighChem*
Level of qualification: *null*
Form of study: *null*
Date of beginning of the studies: *01.10.2018*
Date of admission to the study programme: *01.10.2018*

INFORMATION ON THE RESULTS GAINED

Courses by didactic cycles	Type/No. of hrs	Grade	ECTS
<i>Academic year 2018/2019</i>			
<i>(02-CCB2G) Career Core Box - do you [truly] THINK about ypur scientific career?</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-PDFG) Przygotowanie do dydaktyki szczegółowej – chemia fizyczna i teoretyczna</i>	<i>sem 13</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SGBNG) Seminarium grupy badawczej</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SMTG) Small Molecule Tools in Modern Chemical Biology</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[3,5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-TAS2G) Talking about science to non scientific audiences</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-PZG) Training in teaching academic classes</i>	<i>cw 90</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>(02-WPBNG) Wstęp do prowadzenia badań naukowych</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>Academic year 2018/2019, summer semester</i>			
<i>(03-KJP4-SL) Polish language course (4 hours per week)</i>	<i>lek 60</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Academic year 2019/2020</i>			
<i>(02-ABC2G) ABC of Research Integrity in the European Research Area</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-DPEG) Design principles for nanoporous carbo-based materials in Energy Storage and Energy Conversion Applications</i>	<i>wyk 15</i>	<i>[4,5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-HIR2G) How to manage international research project. Best way of being the good manager.</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SGBG) Research group seminar</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(56-RUT) Rethinking university teaching.</i>	<i>war 15</i>	<i>[4,5]</i>	<i>5</i>
<i>(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[3]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-SN2G) Sympozium naukowe</i>	<i>wyk</i>	<i>[4]</i>	<i>1</i>
<i>(02-PZG) Training in teaching academic classes</i>	<i>cw</i>	<i>[5]</i>	<i>4</i>
<i>Academic year 2019/2020, winter semester</i>			
<i>(02-CRIA) Crystallography I: Elements</i>	<i>wyk 15 / lab 30</i>	<i>[3,5/3]</i>	<i>5</i>

Courses by didactic cycles	Type/No. of hrs	Grade	ECTS
<i>Academic year 2020/2021</i>			
(02-HCG) Heterogeneous catalysis – a pillar of the green chemistry and sustainable development	wyk 12	[3]	1
(02-NATG) Nucleic acid-targeting molecular systems: from chemistry to biomedical applications	wyk 15	[5]	1
(02-SGBG) Research group seminar	cw	[5]	1
(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe	wyk	[4]	1
(02-PZG) Training in teaching academic classes	cw	[4]	4
<i>Academic year 2021/2022</i>			
(02-ACW2G) Academic writing	war 15	[4]	1
(02-MOC2G) Mechanochemical organic and coordination chemistry	cw 18	[5]	1
(02-SGBG) Research group seminar	cw	[3]	1
(02-SADSG) Self-assembly of dynamic systems	wyk 10	[3]	1
(02-SEWG) Seminarium wydziałowe	wyk	[3]	1
(02-SSPA2G) Soft skills - the practical approach	war 30	[5]	2
(02-STA2G) Statistics	war 15	[4]	1
(02-SN2G) Sympozium naukowe	wyk	[4]	1
(02-OCBVG) The Organic Chemistry of the B Vitamins	wyk 10	[3]	
ECTS in total:			52

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 +48 61 829 16 04

Signature and name stamp of the head of a doctoral programme

Official seal of the University

The University uses the following grading scheme

very good	5
good plus	4,5
good	4
satisfactory plus	3,5
satisfactory	3
unsatisfactory	2
credit	zal
no credit	nzal

Description of class type codes

cw	classes
lab	laboratory
lek	course
sem	seminar
war	workshop
wyk	lecture

Grades outside brackets are course grades, grades inside brackets are grades for the classes, vertical bar separates grades for various classes, semicolon separates grades on various exam reports, space separates grades on the same exam report, order of grades on a report follows order of exam sessions.

ZAL (zaliczenie) = non-graded pass, NZAL (niezaliczenie) = fail, -- = no grade in the examination protocol.

Dr. Amirali R. Davoudpour

Nationality: **Iranian**

Date of birth: **16/09/1979**

Tel: **(+48) 513467771**

Email address: **davoudpour@irapolska.eu**

Social Media*:

LinkedIn:

www.linkedin.com/in/amirali-r-davoudpour-990833156

ORCID:

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2569-0410>

Google Scholar:

<https://scholar.google.pl/citations?user=72A7OQkAAAAJ&hl=en>

Researchgate:

<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Amirali-R-Davoudpour>

*Only approved social media are listed

Summary:

I am a dedicated researcher with a passion for cutting-edge research and a track record of impactful contributions to the scientific community. Proficient in utilizing advanced analytical techniques to investigate complex biological phenomena. Adept at presenting research findings in international conferences and publishing in reputable scientific journals. Seeking to further my career in scientific exploration and make meaningful contributions to the advancement of knowledge.

WORK EXPERIENCE

Canon of Medicine and Law in Iran , [10/2023- Now]

secretary

Address: Tehran-Iran (Remote)

Adam-Mickiewicz University of Poznan [11/2018 – 29/09/2022]

Ph.D. student

Address: Poznan (Poland)

Julius-Maximilians University of Würzburg [06/2012 – 12/2015]

Research associate at Bioimaging center

Address: Würzburg (Germany)

Biophotonic manipulation of GPCRs

Ludwig-Maximilians University of München [03/2011 – 06/2012]

Research associate at Institute of Cardiovascular Prevention,

Address: München (Germany)

Heterodimerization of chemokines, expression and purification of CXCL8 (IL8) and CCL2 (MCP1) chemokines

University of Lübeck [03/2010 – 02/2011]

Internship at institute of Molecular Medicine

Address: Lübeck (Germany)

Fluorescence based nucleic acid binding studies of various DNA polymerases and human Ago2 protein

Iran Institute of Plant Protection [06/2006 – 02/2007]

Research assistant at Iranian Institute of Plant Protection

Address: Tehran (Iran)

Master thesis, Azad University of Tehran

Enhancing the efficacy of Fusarium spp. for microbial control of *O. aegyptiaca*

Language proficiency

- **English:** Fluent in scientific communication, with published works in international journals.
- **German:** Intermediate in reading and conversation for academic and research purposes.
- **Turkish:** Conversational proficiency for collaboration with colleagues.
- **Persian:** Native language.
- **Arabic:** Proficient in reading for literature review and research purposes.

Education

- **Ph.D. in Biochemistry,**

Canon of Medicine and Law [30/12/2013], Tehran-Iran

Collaborative Ph.D. studentship in Adam-Mickiewicz University in Poznan-Poland [10/2018 – 29/09/2022]

Title of Dissertation: *Analysis of antioxidant capacity of red blood cells in oxidative stress conditions utilizing fluorescent lifetime imaging microscopy (FLIM),*

[10.13140/RG.2.2.22634.90569](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.22634.90569)

- **M.Sc. in Biology/Microbiology**

Science and research campus of Azad University of Tehran-Iran [09/2002 – 09/2005]

Title of Dissertation: Enhancing the efficacy of *Fusarium* spp. for microbial control of *Orobanche aegyptiaca* [10.13140/RG.2.2.16036.65928](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.16036.65928)

B.Sc. of Biology/Microbiology

Karaj Azad University [09/1997 – 01/2002]

High school diploma

Alborz High School Tehran-Iran [09/1993 – 06/1997]

PUBLICATIONS

RISC in development; A review on RNA Induced Silencing Complex and its contribution to cellular differentiation, International Journal of Hematology-Oncology and Stem Cell Research, **Amirali Davoudpour.**, 2011, ISSN: 2008-3009, eISSN: 2008-2207

Photophysical properties of alloxazine derivatives with extended aromaticity – Potential redox-sensitive fluorescent probe, Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy, Anna Golczak, Małgorzata Insińska-Rak, **Amirali Davoudpour**, Daban Hama Saeed, Petra Ménova, Viktor Mojr Radek Cibulka, Igor Khmelinski, Lucyna Mrówczyńska, Marek Sikorski, Volume 272, 5 May 2022, 120985, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2022.120985>

Preprints:

Application of a ROS-FRET Ruler for Measurement of Fluorescence Mediated Antibody Unbinding, Davoudpour et al.

Analysis of human red blood cell's intrinsic fluorescence lifetime using phasor transformation and FLIM histogram, Davoudpour et al.

Double spectral analysis of RBC intrinsic fluorescence lifetime to determine mechanism of tert-butyl hydroperoxide oxidative stress and Trolox using FLIM and phasor approach, Davoudpour et al.

Photobiology and dynamics of selected flavins/alloxazines in a simulated synthetic heterogenous membrane, Davoudpour et al.

CONFERENCES AND SEMINARS

Characterization of photochemical properties of human red blood cells in oxidative stress conditions by fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy; Amirali Davoudpour, Zubair Anwar, Lucyna Mrówczyńska, Tomasz Pędziński, Jacek L Kolanowski, Marek Sikorski, 22nd international conference on oxidative stress reduction, redox homeostasis and anti-oxidants, **Paris-France(Online)**, October 2020(Oral presentation) DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30716.72325

Fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy of human red blood cells in oxidative stress conditions; Amirali Davoudpour, Zubair Anwar, Lucyna Mrówczyńska, Tomasz Pędziński, Jacek L Kolanowski, Marek Sikorski, International Conference of Advanced Materials and Applications, **Banglore-India (Online)**, September 2020 (Oral

presentation)

Analysis of fluorescence lifetime distribution of human red blood cells in redox conditions; Amirali Davoudpour,, Lucyna Mrówczyńska, Tomasz Pędziński, Jacek L Kolanowski, Marek Sikorski, Polish Photoscience Seminar,*Swietokrzyska Polana-Poland*, June-2019(Oral presentation)

Manipulation of protein-protein interactions by photounbinding; Amirali Davoudpour and Katrin G. Heinze, Focus on Microscopy, *Göttingen-Germany*, March-2015 (Oral presentation) DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22747.54564

Towards mechanism of photounbinding; Amirali Davoudpour and Katrin G. Heinze, International microscopy conference, *Prague-Czech republic*, Sep-2014 (Poster presentation)

Biophotonic manipulation of GPCRs; Amirali Davoudpour and Katrin G. Heinze, Eureka 2014 international symposium organized by the students of the Graduate School of Life Sciences *Würzburg-Germany*-Oct 2014(Poster presentation)

Biophotonic manipulation of GPCRs; Amirali Davoudpour and Katrin G. Heinze, Scientific cross-talk, international symposium organized by the students of the Graduate School of Life Sciences *Würzburg-Germany*-Oct 2013(Poster presentation)

JOB-RELATED SKILLS

- **Coding on demand: Python, C++, Mql4 (intermediate)**
 - **Neural networks, Machine learning, Data Science (intermediate level)**
 - **Labview (basics)**
 - **Schrodinger software**
 - **CHARMM GUI**
 - **Docking and lead databases, Molecular dynamics (GROMACS), ChemDraw, ChemView ...**
- **Fluorescence Life Time Imaging Microscopy (FLIM)**

Fluorescence microscopy: Confocal (Leica SP5)

Fluorescence Resonance Energy Transfer (FRET)

- **Fluorescence spectroscopy (FLS)**
- **High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC)**

Fast Protein Liquid Chromatography(FPLC)

Bacteria and Cell culture techniques

DNA & RNA extraction and purification

Dynamic light scattering (DLS)

Fluorescence Activated Cell Sorting (FACS)

Teaching duties:

Adam-Mickiewicz university in Poznan-Poland

2021/SZ Spectroscopy laboratory(02-SPXCA)

2021/SL Blood physiology laboratory (01-W-BTA-FIZBLOOD)

2021/SL Physical Chemistry laboratory (02-PHYX)

Business expertise

- **Startups:**

- Manager at Farid Farsi Tejarat Yaran Alborz LLC reg 573997. [2018-current]
- Manager at IraPolska SPÓŁKA Z OGRANICZONĄ ODPOWIEDZIALNOŚCIĄ, KRS nr. 0000967349, REGON 52178692200000, NIP 7831855512 [2022- Current]